

The utility of Karate training in later life for healthy ageing

By

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Abstract

World population is ageing causing increased costs for public health and some social issues, mostly for seniors. Scientific literature has shown that physical exercises and a socially active lifestyle could lead to a better quality of life and longevity. Nevertheless, the general senior population is too inactive. The issue became even bigger during the Covid-19 pandemic, when elderly people were forced to isolate, staying at home, becoming consequently less physically active and lonelier. During the pandemic, remote technologies have been used by people to follow some fitness programs, but the participation of older adults was again extremely low. This confirms that older adults are generally not interested in the proposed programs of physical exercise. Few exceptions seem to be represented by martial arts. Tai Chi is the most popular and suggested physical activity for seniors, but it is not the most popular martial art, as instead is Karate, which on the contrary is not very well known by scientific literature. Considering the low success of actual physical activity programs, the researcher has started to consider the popular Karate, obviously adapted, as an easy way to involve older adults, thanks to remote technologies, to keep participants safe according to the Covid-19 safety guidelines. This culminated in the following thesis aims:

- To literary review previously published research on ageing and martial arts.
- To investigate possible psycho-social benefits of traditional martial arts in different age groups
- To lead a review on previously published material on Karate, health, and well-being.

- To investigate the feasibility and acceptability of an online adapted Karate class for the elderly.

As a result of these aims, this thesis had 3 hypotheses:

- Adapted Karate practice could be associated with greater health and quality of life in the elderly.
- Karate could represent the definitive activity to promote active ageing and involve older adults in physical activity
- Increased health and quality of life in the elderly could result in greater social resources and less public health expenditure

In addressing these aims, 5 original investigations are presented

Study 1- “The literary review”. The aim of this review was to identify possible benefits on health in older adults from the practice of martial arts.

Study 2- “The pilot study 1”. This pilot study aimed to evaluate coping skills and self-esteem in Karate competitors.

Study 3- “The pilot study 2”. The aim of the study was to investigate the role of martial arts and their dojos, in the community, to improve quality of life, physical activity, and social involvement in later life.

Study 4- “The scoping review”. In this study, the author has tried to identify possible proven correlations between Karate and health, in previously published research.

Study 5- “Feasibility and acceptability of an online Karate intervention”. This last investigation has the goal to verify if an online adapted Karate class intervention is feasible and acceptable for older adults.

In conclusion, this original thesis provides a new perspective on the use of adapted Karate for health purposes in later life and finds in Karate a new original solution to involve older adults in physical and social activities contributing to a better and healthier quality of life. The research is also of primary importance for Karate instructors and federations as it gives the first practical guidelines of an adapted protocol for elderly people.

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Table of contents

The utility of Karate training in later life for healthy ageing	1
Abstract	2
Acknowledgments	4
Chapter I: Active ageing and martial arts, a literature review	8
Demography and costs of an ageing	9
Life in later age	13
Physical and psychological consequences of ageing	17
Barriers to activity	28
Martial arts for an ageing population	28
The promotion of Tai Chi	30
The myths of “the slower the better”	31
Martial arts and psychological well-being in the elderly.	34
Karate: a suitable martial art for older adults?	37
Focus on Karate: background on history, culture and health	37
Karate health benefits across different age-groups	38
The importance of this research for public health and Karate federations	40
Reasons for participation in older Karatekas / martial artists	41
Critique of previous research and scope for improvement	43
Rationale and aims	44
Chapter II: Scoping Review – Health Benefits of Karate	47
Introduction	48
Methods	50
Results	52
Main themes	60
Musculoskeletal health	60
Balance	63
Cardiovascular health	65
Metabolic effects	66
Neurophysiology	68
Psychology and behaviour	70
	6

Discussion	72
Limitations	76
Conclusions	77
Chapter III: Dojo and martial arts: a social community for physical activity and healthy ageing	79
Introduction	80
Methods	82
Results	86
Discussion	92
Conclusions	94
Chapter IV: Age, Karate Participation and Self-esteem and Coping	95
Introduction	96
Methods	98
Results	100
Discussion	108
Limitations	111
Conclusions	111
Chapter V: Feasibility of an online Karate intervention for elderly people	112
Introduction	113
The importance of being physically active	114
COVID-19	115
Why Karate?	115
Methods	117
Intervention	118
Results	122
Discussions	125
Limitations	128
Conclusions	129
Chapter VI- General Discussion	130
References	133

Chapter I: Active ageing and martial arts, a literature review

Ageing and physical activity

Demography and costs of ageing

The global population is ageing fast, experiencing serious health issues, falls, and balance impairments¹. While ageing is inevitable, population ageing affects some areas more than others. Over the next 15 years, the number of older persons is expected to grow fastest in Latin America and the Caribbean with a projected 71% increase in the population aged ≥ 60 years of age, followed by Asia (66%) and Africa (64%). Europe and northern America are projected to have a slower population growth of older adults compared with other regions².

Table 1.1 Population aged 60 years or over and aged 80 years or over for the world, development groups, regions, and income groups, 2000, 2015, 2030 and 2050. [[Data source: United Nations (2015). World population prospects: the 2015 revision²]

	Person aged 60 years or over (million)				Percentage change		Distribution of older persons (percentage)			
	2000	2015	2030	2050	2000-2015	2015-2030	2000	2015	2030	2050
World	607.1	900.9	1402.4	2092	48.4	55.7	100	100	100	100
Development groups										
More developed regions	231.3	298.8	375.2	421.4	29.2	25.6	38.1	33.2	26.8	20.1
Less developed regions	375.7	602.1	1027.2	1670.5	60.3	70.6	61.9	66.8	73.2	79.9
Other less-developed countries	341.9	550.1	938.7	1484.9	60.9	70.6	53.6	61.1	66.9	71.0
Least developed countries	33.9	52.1	88.5	185.6	53.8	70.0	5.6	5.8	6.3	8.9
Regions										
Africa	42.4	64.4	105.4	220.3	51.9	63.5	7.0	7.2	7.5	10.5
Asia	319.5	508.0	844.5	129.7	59.0	66.3	52.6	56.4	60.2	61.8
Europe	147.3	176.5	217.2	242.0	19.8	23.1	24.3	19.6	15.5	11.6
Latin American/Caribbean	42.7	70.9	121.0	200.0	66.1	70.6	7.0	7.9	8.6	9.6
Oceania	4.1	6.5	9.6	13.2	56.2	47.4	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.6
Northern America	51.0	74.6	104.8	122.7	46.4	40.5	8.4	8.3	7.5	5.9
Income groups										
High-Income Countries	210.8	309.7	408.9	483.1	34.2	32.0	38.0	34.4	29.2	23.1
Upper-middle-income countries	195.2	320.2	544.9	800.6	64.0	70.2	32.1	35.5	38.9	38.3
Lower-middle-income countries	159.7	237.5	393.9	692.5	48.8	65.9	26.3	26.4	28.1	33.1

Low-income countries	21.2	33.2	54.0	114.8	56.2	61.0	3.5	3.7	3.9	5.5
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Table 1.2 Population aged 80 years or over and aged 80 years or over for the world, development groups, regions, and income groups, 2000, 2015, 2030 and 2050. [Data source: United Nations (2015). World population prospects: the 2015 revision²]

	Person aged 80 years or over (million)				Percentage change		Distribution of older persons (percentage)			
	2000	2015	2030	2050	2000-2015	2015-2030	2000	2015	2030	2050
World	71.0	125.3	201.8	434.4	76.5	61.1	100	100	100	100
Development groups										
More developed regions	36.5	59.1	85.2	127.8	61.8	41.4	51.5	47.2	42.2	29.4
Less developed regions	34.4	66.2	116.6	306.7	92.1	76.3	48.5	52.8	57.8	70.6
Other less-developed countries	32.0	61.4	108.2	285.9	91.6	76.3	45.1	49.0	53.6	65.8
Least developed countries	2.4	4.8	8.4	20.7	99.2	75.4	3.4	3.8	4.2	4.8
Regions										
Africa	3.0	5.7	9.3	22.2	85.7	64.3	4.3	4.5	4.6	5.1
Asia	30.9	60.0	103.9	255.7	94.0	71.0	43.6	47.9	51.4	58.8
Europe	21.2	34.6	46.1	71.0	63.0	33.2	29.9	27.6	22.8	26.4
Latin American/Caribbean	5.1	10.3	18.7	44.8	103.4	81.4	7.2	8.2	9.3	10.3
Oceania	0.7	1.1	2.0	3.6	69.8	76.8	1.0	0.9	1.0	0.8
Northern America	10.0	13.6	22.0	17.2	36.1	61.7	14.1	10.9	10.9	8.6
Income groups										
High-Income Countries	37.0	60.9	90.9	145.4	64.5	49.3	52.2	48.6	45.0	33.5
Upper-middle-income countries	19.0	37.2	66.6	182.5	96.2	79.0	26.7	29.7	33.0	42.0

Lower-middle-income countries	13.5	24.4	39.3	94.8	80.9	61.1	19.0	19.5	19.5	21.8
Low-income countries	1.5	2.7	4.9	11.3	83.6	80.9	2.1	2.2	2.4	2.6

Currently, the number of older adults (≥ 65 years of age) in Europe, represents 19% of the total population³. Statistical projections indicate that, by 2050, 17% of the world's population (1.6 billion people) will be ≥ 65 years of age⁴. In the united kingdom (UK) an increase in the population aged ≥ 60 years from 17 % in 2010 to around 23 % by 2035 is expected⁵. The most rapid rise is projected for the 'oldest' old, where the number of people aged ≥ 85 years of age is expected to increase from 1.4 million to around 3.5 million⁵. Older populations are primarily females, due to greater life expectancy than males. In 2015, women accounted for 54% of the global population aged 60 years or over and 61% of those aged 80 years or over².

Figure 1 The population aged 60-79 years and aged 80 years or over by development group, 2000, 2015, 2030 and 2050

Data source: United Nations (2015). World population prospects: the 2015 revision.²

Life in later age

The increase in our ageing population presents several public health challenges that governments need to prepare for as people are living longer, but not healthier⁴. It is important to introduce the concept of health span, which is not synonymous with lifespan (the life expectancy at birth, at the moment around 73 years⁶). Health span is considered the period of life where one is living free from serious diseases that are causes of death⁷. According to the World Health Organisation (W.H.O.), the health span is shorter

than the lifespan as we live 20% of our lives unhealthily⁷. In Scotland, for example, where there is the lowest lifespan of all health spans has decreased to 61.7 years for men and 61.9 years for females, while the lifespan is around 77.1 years for males and 81.1 years for females⁸. Therefore, living longer does not mean good health and good quality of life at a later age.

An important aspect of healthspan is that ageing is associated with several non-communicable diseases, for example, cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes and neurodegenerative diseases that have greatly increased from 2005 to 2013^{9,10}. According to the Centres for disease control and prevention, in the u.s.a. heart disease cost the health care system \$216 billion per year, the cost of cancer care continues to rise and is expected to reach almost \$240 billion by 2030, while in 2017, the total estimated cost of diagnosed diabetes was \$327 billion and by 2050 the costs of some neurodegenerative disease as Alzheimer's are projected to be more than \$1.1 trillion¹¹. The repercussion of this is a greater risk of functional loss and disability¹⁰. These health issues have been associated with greater public health care expenditure. For example, a 70-year-old person with functional limitations has cumulative healthcare expenditures of about 145,000 dollars until death¹². Osteoporosis is one of the most common age-related disease¹³. In the united states of America (USA), osteoporosis-related healthcare expenditure, and in 2002 was estimated to be 14 billion us dollars¹⁴, while in the UK the cost of residential care for a person aged 65 and over is £565 a week and for nursing care is £606 a week .¹⁵

Societal effects of ageing and ageism prejudices and stereotypes on ageing may lead to ageism. Ageism, according to Larsen and Solem is as “negative or positive stereotypes, prejudice and/or discrimination against (or to the advantage of) elderly people on the basis of their chronological age or on the basis of a perception of them as being ‘old’ or ‘elderly’^{16,17}. Ageism can be implicit or explicit and can be expressed on a “micro, meso, or macro level” (p. 15). It is particularly interesting because along with incorporating

cognitive, affective and behavioural aspects, as well as conscious and unconscious dimensions, this definition also emphasises the importance of the individual, social and institutional factors¹⁶. It is necessary to break prejudices regarding the elderly as these can discourage elderly people from freely participating in work or recreational activities and, furthermore, prejudices can contribute to the social isolation of the oldest generations, limiting their ability to make a positive contribution to the collective whole, and perpetuating fear of ageing in all individuals^{16,18}

Population ageing has social consequences and it has been a European and global policy to promote older people's active participation in society (e.g., in the labour market, in volunteering, informal care provision, and political participation)¹⁹. Active ageing is a broad concept focused on encouraging the participation of older adults in society, not exclusively in the labour market. Active ageing has been defined as "a process of optimising opportunities for health, participation, and security in order to enhance the quality of life as people age, not just the ability to be physically active"¹⁹. Similarly, the laboratory for integrative lifespan research at the Victoria University in Canada describes active ageing as the maintenance of positive subjective well-being, good physical, social and mental health and continued involvement in one's family, peer group and community throughout the ageing process²⁰. Active ageing involves individual and social domains that range from personal and familial, to social and professional²¹. Therefore, it seems that the concept of active ageing is wide and involves health-related issues but social ones too.

Keeping older adults socially involved is a health priority too, as social relationships are important for health²². Loneliness is a subjective feeling of dissatisfaction with one's social relationships. Being socially isolated or lonely (e.g. Having few contacts, little involvement in social activities, and living alone) is linked with increased mortality, increased incidence of heart disease and functional

decline²². Older people are especially exposed to loneliness and social isolation²³. According to Age UK, more than 2 million people in England over the age of 75 live alone, and more than a million older people say they go over a month without speaking to a friend, neighbour, or family member²³. Isolation and social interaction have health effects²⁴. For example, being isolated or lonely may contribute to frailty because loneliness may alter the tendency of cells in the immune system to promote inflammation and to build up plaque in arteries, help cancer cells grow and spread, and promote inflammation in the brain leading to Alzheimer's disease²⁵. Research has linked social isolation and loneliness to higher risks for a variety of physical and mental conditions: high blood pressure, heart disease, obesity, a weakened immune system, anxiety, depression, cognitive decline, Alzheimer's disease, and even death²⁵.²⁴. The cause of these cross-sectional associations is unclear but a possibility is that being frail leads to increases in loneliness and social isolation²². On the other hand, performing low levels of physical activity associated with social inclusion could result in frailty, so this relationship may be bidirectional²². Frailty is a clinical syndrome whose main feature is heightened vulnerability to stressors due to lowered physiological reserves, a decline in the ability to maintain homeostasis, and impairments in multiple systems^{22,26}. Frailty is strongly associated with loneliness and social isolation^{22,27}. Thus, it is imperative to keep older adults socially involved and physically active to enhance their health and well-being. Unfortunately, one of the biggest barriers to an active lifestyle at a later age is the general idea or stereotype of ageing, mostly related to sickness and weakness⁹. Stereotypes about ageing, beyond influencing behaviour, can also impact personal experiences and self-perception of ageing. There are associations between negative self-perceptions and cardiovascular functioning¹⁶. More specifically, negative self-perception of ageing involves reduced self-efficacy, which directly affects depression, and exerts repercussions for physical health due to effects on the immune system and on the cardiovascular

system¹⁶. Meanwhile, positive self-perceptions of ageing are associated with higher levels of well-being, better health, and/or longevity^{16,28}.

Physical and psychological consequences of ageing

The reasons why we age biologically are not entirely clear²⁹. According to the literature, theories of ageing fall into two main categories: programmed and damage or error theories. In addition, the theories interact with each other and are not to be considered only individually²⁹. The programmed theories imply that ageing follows a biological timetable, perhaps a continuation of the one that regulates childhood growth and development¹². The programmed theory has three sub-categories: 1) programmed longevity. Ageing is the result of a sequential switching on and off of certain genes, with senescence being defined as the time when age-associated deficits are manifested. 2) endocrine theory: hormones control the pace of ageing. 3) immunological theory. The immune system is programmed to decline over time, which leads to an increased vulnerability to infectious disease and thus ageing and death¹².

The damage or error theory includes 1) wear and tear theory. Cells and tissues have vital parts that wear out resulting in ageing. 2) rate of living theory. The greater an organism's rate of oxygen basal metabolism, the shorter its lifespan. 3) cross-linking theory. An accumulation of cross-linked proteins damages cells and tissues, slowing down bodily processes resulting in ageing. 4) free radicals theory. Free radicals damage cells resulting in dysfunctions and ageing. 5) somatic DNA damage theory. DNA damages occur continuously in the cells of living organisms. While most of these damages are repaired, some accumulate, as the DNA polymerases and other repair mechanisms cannot correct defects as fast as they are apparently produced, causing ageing²⁹. Whatever the reason, when we age, we are much more exposed to cognitive and physical decline^{30,31}.

A reduction of muscle mass, strength, physical endurance, coordination and balance, joint flexibility and mobility, cardiovascular and respiratory function, bone strength, and an increase in body fat, blood pressure, susceptibility to mood disorders such as anxiety and depression, and various diseases including cardiovascular disease and stroke, are common consequences of physical decline among elderly.³¹

Pertinent to the older adult, muscle strength declines from <40 years to those >40 years between 17% and 41%^{31,32}. Loss of muscle mass and muscle strength, termed *sarcopenia*, is one of the leading causes of disability in the elderly³³. Ageing-related changes in skeletal muscle power begin to decline after the age of 30 years of age and continue to decline linearly with advancing age³⁴. Therefore, although sarcopenia is a disease associated with older adults, it has its origins in middle-age and potentially earlier. Impairments in muscle strength and power have robust associations with mobility limitations, and resistance training is effective at improving these impairments and mobility performance³⁵

The aforementioned degeneration in muscular properties increases the risk of falling in older adults³⁶. These compound the loss of balance experienced in older age which also increases fall risk, and fragility of bone which increases fall repercussions (i.e. Bone breakages)³⁶. In this context, balance is reduced via changes in somatosensation, vision, and vestibular function which all have a negative impact on maintaining postural balance, resulting in an increased risk of falling, and increased fear of falling³⁴.

The ideal intervention to slow muscle degeneration is multi-modal and may involve resistance exercise, aerobic exercise, nutrition, and psychosocial components³⁵. The ACSM recommends a training frequency of 2-4 days per week, a training volume of 1-3 sets of 8-12 repetitions across 6-12 exercises targeting the major muscle groups, and a loading of 60-80% of 1 repetition maximum (1 RM)³⁵. This

kind of training shows to be effective but very difficult to be performed in daily life as a pragmatic intervention³⁵. Therefore, there is a need for alternative solutions to slow muscle degeneration.

Slowing the process of muscle degeneration is important to slow the degeneration of cognitive functions too³⁷. Cognitive impairment associated with increased age is a major health and social issue. Cognitive decline is one of the most common aspects of growing old and is also the most expensive³⁸. Cognitive decline heralds dementia, illness and death and in the UK, cognitive failure is the cause of 40% of admissions to institutional care³⁸. Older brain age has been associated with mild cognitive impairment, Alzheimer's disease and related dementias, and mortality³⁹⁻⁴¹. Individuals with an older brain age are more likely to have risk factors for dementia including obesity, diabetes, alcoholism, and traumatic brain injury⁴⁰. Cognitive and physical impairment are usually interconnected as many studies show that classification and assessment of the severity of cognitive impairment often depend on physical function status⁴². Further understanding of the interrelationship between cognitive and physical function is needed in frail populations because these individuals are at the highest risk for functional dependence and major health-related events^{42,43}.

Therefore, cognitive health and muscle strength seem to be two important factors for a successful ageing⁴⁴. Successful ageing, according to Kim and Park involves the following domains: avoiding disease and disability, having a high cognitive, mental and physical function, being actively engaged in life, and being psychologically well adapted in later life⁴⁴. A successful ageing is a step forward to healthy ageing that is defined by the world health organisation as "the process of developing and maintaining the functional ability that enables well-being in older age⁴⁵." Functional ability is about having the capabilities that enable all people to be and do what they have reason to value. This includes a person's ability to:

- Meet their basic needs;
- Learn, grow and make decisions;
- Be mobile;
- Build and maintain relationships; and
- Contribute to society⁴⁵.

In order to do so, one more significant consideration for healthy ageing is related to the environment⁴⁶. For a healthy ageing, older adults should keep the agency in their lives, including the ability to exert control over their environment⁴⁶. Unfortunately, even if design decisions have a significant impact on the health and well-being of older adults, but these decisions are often made in the absence of strong scientific evidence⁴⁶.

Another important aspect of healthy ageing is the consideration that people have for themselves. Self-esteem is linked with well-being, life satisfaction and health⁴⁷. Self-esteem is related to peoples' capacities to cope with life events, including physical and cognitive decline⁴⁷. It can be defined as the overall affective evaluation of one's worth, value or importance⁴⁸ a cross-sectional study with a sample of 589 men and 684 women from the general Spanish population aged 65 - 94 years revealed self-esteem might be related to gender in elderly⁴⁹. Matud et al. evaluated all participants with questionnaires and scales to assess psychological distress, social functioning, stress, coping styles, self-esteem, and social support. Women scored higher than men in psychological distress, chronic stress, emotional coping and instrumental social support, whereas men scored higher than women in self-esteem and rational coping, suggesting that psychological distress was significantly associated in women and men with lower self-esteem and that it was affected by sex⁴⁹. Psychological distress has been related to increasing rates of

death from several major causes, such as cerebral disease, cardiovascular disease, cancer and deaths from external causes and it has been negatively associated with age and with self-esteem⁴⁹.

Excessive or accumulated stress can accelerate epigenetic ageing, affect autonomic dysregulation, impact the immune system by secreting hormones that also change with age, and negatively affect cognition⁴⁹. On the other hand, the effects of stress can be moderated by other variables such as coping and social support⁴⁹

Coping refers to the conscious effort, to solve personal and interpersonal problems, and to try to master, minimise or tolerate stress and conflict⁵⁰. Previous research suggests self-esteem is affected by age and that average levels of self-esteem increase from age 4 to 11 years, remain stable from age 11 to 15 years, increase strongly until age 30 years, continue to increase until aged 60 years where it peaks, and remain constant until aged 70 years, decline until age 90 years, decline more rapidly from 90 years of age onwards⁵¹. If self-esteem is one of the coping components, it seems obvious that when it changes, coping changes too. Furthermore, chronic health problems in the elderly are little controllable and cognitive emotion-focused coping modes seem to be necessary⁵². Positive reappraisal or “the cognitive strategy for reframing a situation to see it in a positive light” shows to be associated with higher well-being and physical health, while rumination, or “the negative recurrent thoughts and/or images”, is associated with a decrease in the quality of life for older adults of their psychological, physical, and cognitive health⁵²

Unfortunately, there are scant studies related to coping and age, but new research has observed changes in coping strategies related to increased age⁵³. One of the ways to measure self-esteem is the Rosenberg

self-esteem scale, which seems the most widely used self-report instrument for evaluating individual self-esteem in the literature⁵⁴.

Ageing/activity and health

Physical activity and structured exercise are currently considered essential interventions within the primary and secondary healthcare framework as they have been associated with reduced risk of several chronic conditions such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, cancer, hypertension, obesity, depression, osteoporosis, balance problems, and difficulty walking^{55,56}. According to the W.H.O., physical activity is a bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles, and which requires energy expenditure, this includes activities undertaken while working, playing, carrying out household chores, travelling, and engaging in recreational pursuits⁵⁷. "Physical exercise" or "exercise" is a subcategory of physical activity that is planned, structured, repetitive, and aims to improve or maintain one or more components of physical fitness⁵⁷. Both moderate- and vigorous-intensity physical activity improve health⁵⁷.

Following the W.H.O., for health improvements, adults aged 18–64 years should do 150 minutes of moderate-intensity physical activity each week, or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity physical activity each week, or a combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity⁵⁷. Adults should increase their moderate-intensity physical activity to 300 minutes per week, or equivalent. It is recommended to do muscle-strengthening exercises 2 or more days a week, involving major muscle groups⁵⁷.

In order to maintain a healthy weight, adults 65 years and older also need to do 150 minutes of moderate-intensity physical activity during the week or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity physical activity during the week, or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity⁵⁷. Increasing moderate-intensity physical activity to 300 minutes per week, or equivalent will provide additional health

benefits. 3 or more days a week, people with poor mobility should perform physical activity to enhance their balance and prevent falls. Two or more days a week, major muscle groups should be strengthened through muscle-strengthening activities⁵⁷. Depending on the individual, physical activity intensity varies. For cardiorespiratory health, all activity should be performed for at least 10 minutes at a time⁵⁷.

Table 2 Physical activity: definition of moderate and vigorous intensity. [Data source: Michigan State University⁵⁸]

Moderate-intensity Physical activity (approximately 3-6 Mets)	Vigorous-intensity Physical activity (approximately >6 Mets)
Requires a moderate amount of effort and noticeably accelerates the heart rate	Requires a large amount of effort and causes rapid breathing and a substantial increase in heart rate
Examples of moderate-intensity exercise include:	Examples of vigorous-intensity exercise include:
Brisk walking	Running
Dancing	Walking/climbing briskly up a hill
Gardening	Fast cycling
Housework and domestic chores	Aerobics
Traditional hunting and gathering	Fast swimming
Active involvement in games and sports with children/ walking domestic animals	Competitive sports and games (e.g. Traditional games, football, volleyball, hockey, basketball)
General building task	Heavy shovelling or digging ditches

Carrying/moving moderate loads(<20kg)	Carrying/moving heavy loads (>20 kg)
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Metabolic equivalents (METS) are frequently used to express the intensity of physical activities. Met is the ratio of a person's working metabolic rate relative to their resting metabolic rate^{58,59}. One met is defined as the energy cost of sitting quietly and is equivalent to a caloric consumption of 1kcal/kg/hour. It is estimated that compared with sitting quietly, a person's caloric consumption is three to six times higher when being moderately active (3-6 METS) and more than six times higher when being vigorously active (>6 METS)^{58,59}.

Although physical activity brings legitimate health benefits, older people are reluctant to participate in physical activity initiatives⁶⁰. Furthermore, not all physical activity brings the same benefits to the elderly and it can be confusing to choose one activity rather than the other. Both aerobic exercise and resistance exercise have been shown to produce important benefits to health in later life. Aerobic exercise has been demonstrated to improve cognitive functions, cardiovascular health, aerobic fitness and general well-being in later life^{61,62}. Equally, recent evidence highlights the importance of resistance exercise⁶³⁻⁶⁵. Singh et al. Compared the efficacy of physical activity to that of drugs for common age-related conditions and are shedding new light on the relationship between progressive resistance training and health in elderly populations^{66,67}. Exercises designed to stimulate skeletal muscle hypertrophy in congestive heart failure counteract the catabolic effects of circulating cytokines and cannot be achieved with just cardiac medications alone⁶⁷. Exercise can counteract unfavourable side effects of standard medical care, such as resistance training after corticosteroid treatment to prevent proximal myopathy and osteopenia, a potential cause of falls^{67,68}.

One of the major health issues in later life is “falls”⁶⁹, considering that over 30% of people aged 65 or older fall at least once per year^{69,70}. Many studies have shown that the risk of falling can be significantly reduced by prevention programmes based on physical activity⁷¹. To prevent and manage falls, progressive resistance training appears to be a very effective solution that helps to reduce the risk of type 2 diabetes^{72,73}, osteoporosis, sarcopenia^{65,74}, depression^{75,76}, and cognitive decline^{77,78(p1)} too. Higher levels of physical activity reduce the overall morbidity and mortality and the risk of falling between 30% and 50%⁷⁰. Sadly, commonly proposed physical activity programs do not seem to be attractive for seniors, demonstrated by 21.4% of the world being physically inactive⁷⁹. Specifically to fall prevention initiatives, fewer than half of those invited to take part in falls-prevention interventions in the community take up the opportunity.⁶⁰

Besides physical benefits, physical activity helps our psychological well-being. Studies show that three supervised 30 min sessions of aerobic exercise over a period of 16 weeks are sufficient to produce benefits that rival those provided by pharmaceutical antidepressants for patients suffering from both moderate and major depressive disorders⁸⁰. Several studies showed the positive effects of adapted physical activity (APA) on general well-being during the lifetime^{81,82}, evidencing that a 25-week APA program improved static balance, functional mobility, as well as physical functioning, vitality, and general health subdomains of quality of life (QOL) in community-dwelling older adults⁸³. Battaglia et al. (2016) claim that according to researchers and practitioners, physical activity affects QOL in old age via three psychological hypotheses: 1) distraction, 2) self-efficacy, and 3) social relationships. When enjoying physical activities, people distract from unfavourable daily life experiences and this improves their mood after exercise⁸¹. Second, the motivation to complete a physically challenging task was found to be a very important factor for increasing self-concept, self-awareness, and self-determination. Third,

physical activities expose practitioners to opportunities for social interaction, cooperation with others, respecting rules, sharing leisure experiences, and receiving the encouragement of peers”⁸¹.

More specifically, there is a correlation between physical activity and self-esteem. Self-esteem is important for a successful and satisfying life and is a central aspect of psychological well-being⁸⁴. Numerous researchers have examined behavioural influences on self-esteem, and physical activity has been considered to be an important component of positive self-evaluations⁸⁴. Other studies confirm that higher physical activity at ages 9 and 11 years predicted higher self-esteem at ages 11 and 13 and that Tai Chi training is able to improve self-esteem in senior adults too^{85,86}. Sani et al found that self-esteem is strongly affected by body image which changes according to levels of physical activity⁸⁷. This suggests that regular physical activity should be highly promoted among adults with lower self-esteem⁸⁷. Anyway, the correlation between self-esteem and physical activity is not always strong and positive with some previous studies indicating that global self-esteem does not change with physical activity⁸⁸

Physical activity seems effective to improve our coping strategies too. The regular and oriented practice of exercise increases the level of stress coping in elderly people⁷⁷. According to De Andrea et al., the regular and oriented practise of physical exercise improves the level of stress coping in elderly people, and their physical performance in everyday too⁸⁹.

Even during the Covid-19 pandemic, physical exercise was used by older adults in the Japanese community as a coping strategy to manage the stay-at-home period and it was associated with psychological well-being⁹⁰. These findings are supported by the anxiety and depression association of America which confirms the importance of physical exercise to cope with stress⁹¹. However, interventions based on physical activity do not seem to be appealing for older adults as the uptake rates

for fall prevention interventions in the community are typically <50% and are often as low as 10%⁶⁰.

This begs the question, have these programs met the older adults' needs?

Barriers to activity

The way people age depends on physical and social environments and the impact of these environments on their opportunities and health behaviour, creating health inequities^{30,92}. Public health policy must be crafted to reduce these inequities, reducing any barrier that could prevent older adults from participating in physical activity³⁰.

According to the literature, some common barriers to prevent elderly participation in physical activity include insufficient guidance and lack of role models⁹³, fear of falling, fear of overdoing during convalescence after illness, fear of injury or pain (e.g. Back pain or muscle pain), fear for environmental related factors such as fear for exercising outside and fear for going out during the evening, absence of an exercise companion, social opposition (such as being told that pa was inappropriate for elderly persons), high costs exercise programs, time of classes, extreme weather conditions, safety, lack of facilities, bad transportations and ageist stereotypes^{30,93}. To reduce the barriers to physical activity, a comprehensive global strategy and action plan on ageing and health is being developed by whom to address 5 priority areas for action. These areas cover the awareness of the importance of healthy and active ageing, the importance of relating the health system to the needs of older adults, the necessity to develop long-term care action and to create an age-friendly environment, acting on a political level too, keeping track of measurement and progresses³⁰.

Martial arts for an ageing population

Traditional martial arts overview: background on history, culture, and health

Evidence demonstrates that more older adults enjoy the practice of martial arts⁹⁴. Martial arts are an appealing activity⁹⁵ and are widely practised worldwide. According to a 2009 South Korean government survey, there were 70 million people practising taekwondo in 190 countries⁹⁶. One reason for this appeal, and a factor that differentiates traditional martial arts, from modern fighting systems and other sports such as football or swimming, is the organisation of their techniques and tactics into a coherent system, adherence to a philosophy of life or code of conduct, and the coding of effective methods tested in antiquity and modernity⁹⁷. At the same time, traditional martial arts have a very strong link with religion and empathy, considered as the ability to “really feeling what another person is feeling or going to do”⁹⁶.

According to tradition, martial arts were founded around 520 A.D. by Bodhi dharma, a great Buddha who brought Zen Buddhism from India to China⁹⁶. The link between religion and spiritualism is something not to be underestimated, as they have been considered motivational support for physical activity in the elderly⁹⁸.^{54,55}

In terms of healthogenic adaptations, studies have demonstrated that martial arts can decrease the development of osteoporosis, and loss of muscle strength, and decrease the risk of falls in elderly^{99,100}. In a study considering a population with a mean age of 70 years old, a 5-month Karate training programme enhanced attention, resilience, and motor reaction time, while a longer and more intensive training period of 10 months was even more effective¹⁰¹. In fact, the results show that the total scores of the demtect test improved from 16.00 ± 2.15 at baseline to 16.43 ± 1.88 after five months and to 17.09 ± 1.62 after 10 months. The falling length of rod in the rod test decrease from 17.42 ± 7.13 at baseline to 15.53 ± 7.69 after the first five months of intervention, and to 12.20 ± 7.45 , after 10 months, while the median value of total reaction time in the determination test changed from 0.96 ± 0.13 at baseline to 0.92 ± 0.12 after the first five months and to 0.89 ± 0.12 after 10 months.

The promotion of Tai Chi

The most popular or trusted martial art for older adults in modern times is probably Tai Chi¹⁰². During the past 45 years, more than 500 trials and 120 systematic reviews have been published on the health benefits of Tai Chi¹⁰², originally born as a form of Chinese boxing^{103 104}. Developed as a martial art in 13th-century China, Tai Chi is now practised around the world as a health-promoting exercise¹⁰⁵. The interest of the academic literature in Tai Chi, in the past few years, has brought Tai Chi to be considered by different health authorities as a clinical tool especially to improve the quality of life in people over the age of 65¹⁰⁵. The evidence is so strong that Tai Chi is officially recommended by many national health authorities, including the NHS¹⁰⁵. The main reasons for Tai Chi's popularity in the clinical environment are to be found in the fact that this is a “gentle activity, unlikely to cause injury if done correctly, it involves lots of flowing, easy movements without stress in the joints or muscles¹⁰⁵. In this low-impact, slow-motion exercise, athletes perform a series of motions named for animal actions, for example, "white crane spreads its wings" — or martial arts moves, such as "box both ears¹⁰⁶”.

According to Harvard Medical School, “Tai Chi differs from other types of exercise as with circular and not forced movements, the muscles are relaxed rather than tensed, the joints are not fully extended or bent and connective tissues are not stretched, making Tai Chi adaptable for anyone, from the fittest to people confined to wheelchairs¹⁰⁶”. Below, there is a list of the fitness components that Tai Chi can improve such as muscle strength, flexibility, balance, and, to a lesser degree, aerobic conditioning.

Muscle strength. Both lower-body and upper-body strength can be improved by Tai Chi. The benefits of Tai Chi can be comparable to those of resistance training and brisk walking when practised regularly¹⁰⁶.

Flexibility. Tai Chi can boost upper- and lower-body flexibility as well as strength¹⁰⁶.

Balance. According to some studies, Tai Chi improves balance and reduces falls. The ability to sense one's body's position in space, or proprioception, declines as one ages. Tai Chi helps train this sense, which is a function of sensory neurons in the inner ear and stretch receptors in the muscles and ligaments. As a result of Tai Chi, you'll be able to recover from a stumble more quickly because your muscles are stronger and more flexible. People who fear falling are more likely to fall; Tai Chi training helps reduce this fear¹⁰⁶.

Aerobic conditioning. Depending on the speed and size of the movements, Tai Chi can provide some aerobic benefits. Any way to improve cardiorespiratory fitness, research suggests adding some more aerobic training to tai-chi^{105;106}.

However, despite the purported benefits of tai-chi, the focus on using it as the primary martial art for older adults means that the literature might risk to exclude a pool of older athletes and psychophysical benefits that could be investigated in other martial arts such as Karate, taekwondo-do, judo, etc.

If the same health benefits may be gained by practising other physical activities or sports, what makes traditional martial arts special and worthy of investigation, is the link with philosophical, spiritual culture and respect for older adults, which has been considered a determinant for active involvement of aged subjects⁹⁸

The myths of “the slower the better”

According to the National Institute on ageing (NIA), one of the common myths about ageing is “older adults should take it easy and avoid exercise so they don't get injured”¹⁰⁷. This might be explained by the fact that, given age-related reductions in strength, power, and joint stability, the early scientific literature suggested low-intensity, slow movements exercise for older adults to improve their quality of

life¹⁰⁸. Typical low-intensity exercises for older adults include light walking, stretching, lifting hand weights, sit-ups, and push-ups against the wall¹⁰⁸.

This low-impact suggestion of physical activity for older adults can be explained by the fact that older adults are more likely to suffer from mobility impairment¹⁰⁹ and low-intensity exercises are easier to perform and with a very little risk of injury¹⁰⁸. Thinking about a strategy of involvement, this kind of exercise can make the start of an active lifestyle easier, above all for subjects that have previously been sedentary. This might be one of the reasons Tai Chi with its slow and low-impact movements has gained popularity in the clinical field¹⁰⁵.

On the other hand, research has shown that older adults performing moderate to high-intensity physical exercises gain more health benefits than those practising at low intensity¹¹⁰. In fact, in later age, the loss of muscle mass (sarcopenia) and power (dynapenia) are serious health concerns that promote frailty and isolation and are unlikely to be addressed by low-intensity, slow movements^{111,112}. For example, the treatment of loss of muscle mass and muscle strength in older adults is more effective with high-intensity progressive resistance training than with low-intensity progressive resistance training.¹¹³ Resistance training increases muscle strength by 60% to 100% of 1RM (one repetition maximum), and older individuals show similar or greater strength gains as a result of resistance training when compared to younger adults, suggesting preserve muscle plasticity through the lifespan, resulting in the reduction of risk of falls^{63,114}.

The findings seem to align with the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO), which recommends that adults aged 65 years and over exercise at least 150 minutes a week of moderate-intensity activity, or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity activity, or an equivalent combination¹¹⁵. For

additional health benefits, they should increase moderate-intensity physical activity to 300 minutes per week, or equivalent¹¹⁵. It is also advised to practice 2 bouts of muscle-strengthening exercises per week¹¹⁵.

It seems safe to conclude that a dose-response relationship is evident in terms of exercise intensity (dose) and health benefits (response). If low-intensity exercises bring some health benefits and might be effective to involve older adults in physical activity programs, better results and health benefits are likely found in high-intensity exercises^{116,117}.

Martial arts and psychological well-being in the elderly.

The term martial arts is often used as a general phrase to describe combat arts while simultaneously inferring an emphasis on health and philosophical development¹¹⁸. According to Brown, the term martial can be defined as relating to fighting or war; and the term art can be defined as a skill at doing a specified action, typically one acquired through practice^{118,119}. Therefore, martial arts might be defined as any fighting skill acquired through practice⁷⁴. However, this definition does not include the philosophical and health aspects of martial arts.

Typically, martial arts have both internal and external philosophies; internal philosophies include values such as sports character, honour and responsibility, pacifism, nationalism, sacrifice, and civic responsibility, while external philosophies include religions and ethical systems¹¹⁸. Buddhism was linked to Shaolin martial arts in China and neo-Confucianism to Kenjutsu in Japan, for instance¹¹⁸.

Martial arts training is suggested to be efficient for the improvement of mental health and quality of life in different age groups¹²⁰. This is worth investigating to improve the quality of life in the elderly, considering the increasing mental health-related issues of our ageing population.¹²¹

Older people are especially exposed to loneliness and social isolation²³. According to Age UK, more than 2 million people in England over the age of 75 live alone, and more than a million older people say they go for over a month without speaking to a friend, neighbour or family member²³. Loneliness is definitely a risk factor for depression in later life¹²². Depression is a common mental disorder prevalent among elderly people in various countries, with 3.8 per cent to 15 per cent of them having depressive symptoms¹²³. Loneliness is accompanied by feelings of hostility, stress, pessimism, anxiety, and low self-esteem and represents a dispositional tendency that activates neurobiological and behavioural mechanisms contributing to a state of low mood and aversion to activity^{123,124}.

Depression and poor self-esteem tend to be comorbid^{125,126}. People with low self-esteem are at higher risk of depression, and individuals with depression are more likely to feel worthless and inadequate^{24, 25}. Low levels of psychological well-being are associated with functional decline and depression as older individuals with fewer psychological resources, such as coping strategies and social support, are particularly at risk for developing disability¹²⁷. Research has shown that martial arts such as Karate help older adults to have a better emotional well-being¹²⁸. A study by Jansen et al. found that older adults practising Karate improved their emotional mental state, compared to the control group¹²⁸. A different study from Ludivine et al., shows that adapted Karate is able to improve mood and decrease depression in adults aged over 50¹²⁹. Wang et al found that Tai Chi helps to improve mental well-being including depression, anxiety, general stress management, and exercise self-efficacy in various population¹³⁰. At the same time, Bing et al. Show that taekwondo, a traditional Korean martial art, allows people to experience catharsis, which is a mental health effect of sport¹³¹. Therefore, it seems that martial arts training may be a particularly efficacious sports-based mental health intervention, in different age groups, including the elderly, which may provide an inexpensive alternative to psychological therapy^{118,132}. Furthermore, differently from most common interventions such as running or walking, Karate is considered a meaningful activity by practitioners. In fact, martial arts such as Karate bring the subject to be part of a community and promote a broader lifestyle, representing not just 'an activity' but a 'meaningful activity' that is more likely to be sustained in the long-term¹³³. The importance of practising a meaningful activity seems to be growing with age. In fact, the “way of life” motive, as a reason to choose Karate, was significantly more meaningful to subjects of older age (>30 years) or more frequent training¹³³.

Karate: a suitable martial art for older adults?

Focus on Karate: background on history, culture and health

The word Karate can be translated as an empty hand (kara = empty, te = hand)¹³⁴. It is a form of a martial art without any weapons. The early history of Karate is poorly documented¹³⁴. In the 6th century a.d., Bodhi dharma, an Indian Buddhist monk, survived a perilous journey from India to the Shaolin temple in south eastern China by developing physical conditioning through the use of special defence skills and callisthenic exercises and there, he founded what was to become Zen Buddhism and taught the Shaolin monks both exercise and self-defence skills which became the forerunner of China's martial arts, later known as Kung fu¹³⁴. Kung fu spread to Korea and Okinawa, the largest of the Ryukyu Islands. Here, China's martial arts were combined with existing Okinawan self-defence styles to become known as Karate, while in Korea, the same martial art was called Tae Kwon do¹³⁴.

About 1600 AD, the Okinawan government enforced the prohibition of combative activity, but Okinawans secretly continued to develop Karate techniques, causing Karate to flourish as a major martial art that started to gain popularity in the western countries after the World War II¹³⁴. Karate today is a sport recognised by the IOC and approved to enter the Olympic games in 2020, the largest international sport Karate organisation, the world Karate federation (WKF), has more than 10 million members in more than 190-member countries¹³⁵.

The number of people practising Karate in the world was estimated to be in excess of 50 million making it one of the most popular forms of martial arts worldwide¹³⁶. There is a widespread assumption that Karate has similar health benefits as has been reported for other martial arts¹³⁷.

Karate seems to be helpful in improving musculoskeletal health. In fact, some studies show that Karate practitioners have a better bone mineral density (BMD) compared to other athletes¹³⁸. Karate improves lower limb muscle function without increasing the risk of knee injury¹³⁹ and it improves muscle fibre conduction velocity and peak torque¹⁴⁰. Other benefits have been noticed in balance, metabolic effects, neurophysiology, psychology and behaviour. Karate classes are efficient to improve balance and hip strength showing that stabilisation and equilibrium training have helped Karate athletes to improve their muscle strength and balance performance¹⁴¹. It has been also shown that a single session of contact Karate is able to increase post-exercise hypotension¹⁴². Chaabène et al. Suggested Karate athletes' maximal oxygen uptake (VO_{2max}) was greater compared to age-matched controls¹⁴³. Karate practitioners exhibit superior motor reactivity, stress tolerance, and divided attention^{101,144}. Moreover, beneficial effects of Karate on mental health have been observed as it seems capable of reducing anxiety and depression symptoms^{129,145}.

Considering the health benefits of Karate and that tai-chi lacks moderate or vigorous exercise intensity required for physiological adaptation in elderly people, Karate warrants further investigation as it has similar characteristics of other traditional martial arts but includes exercises of a greater intensity.

Karate health benefits across different age-groups

As previously discussed, keeping older adults socially and physically involved is necessary to improve their mental health, physical health and general well-being. Greco et al. Showed that after 12-week Karate training, children with autism spectrum disorder showed greater socio-emotional competence such as communication, cooperation and engagement, better executive functioning ability such as cognitive flexibility, inhibitory control and working memory, and lower aggressiveness, sadness, anxiety and hyperactivity compared to the control group¹⁴⁶.

Karate seems to channel adolescent violence by allowing the expression of simplified, ritualised and regulated aggression and by organising a form of peaceful confrontation with psychological benefits such as self (re)insurance and (re)construction¹⁴⁷. Other studies showed an improvement for Karate practitioners aged over 50 in subjective mental health and anxiety as well as cognitive processing speed¹⁴⁵. Jansen et al. Examined the effects of Karate on measures of mental health in older adults. They randomised fifty-five participants to either 8-weeks of Karate training or a mindfulness-based stress reduction intervention or a control group. They reported that only the Karate group demonstrated improvements in anxiety measured with the hospital anxiety and depression scale (HADS) and mental health measured using the short form 12 (sf12) questionnaire¹⁴⁵. Karate seems to lead to a feeling of self-worth helping to improve older adults' quality of life¹²⁸.

Marie-Ludivine et al. Also investigate the effects of adapted Karate training on the quality of life of middle-aged men. They used a 1-year prospective follow-up study with participants taking part in a 90-minute Karate training session three times per week. They found that adapted Karate training, in subjects aged over 50, has favourable effects on mood, perception of physical health confirmed by better postural control, and improved performance on objective physical testing¹²⁹. 62-witte et al. concluded that there is a significant improvement in motor reactivity, stress tolerance, and divided attention, in elderly subjects, only after the 5-month Karate training period. Additionally, the results of the secondary study indicate further improvements after 10 months^{101(p4)}.

It seems clear that Karate training can be potentially considered as an effective activity to improve social inclusion and physical health during the lifespan and in the senior population too.

The importance of this research for public health and Karate federations

The author believes that this new review could inform public health authorities as it will provide information and data about the most common health and social related issues in later life, a summary on the health benefits of Karate, and will have a new perspective about the potential use of Karate as a clinical tool, that could be more engaging and effective than the actual physical activity initiatives. There is a need for alternative physical activity programmes for older practitioners who want to engage in high-intensity physical exercise to gain more health benefits. This could aid readers to rethink the concept of “the slower the better” for elderly people and start to consider new activities that could be more intense and more challenging from a physical and cognitive perspective.

The review is also very important for Karate federations as it shows the potential use of Karate not only as a sport but as a clinical and health activity across the lifespan. It also brings new opportunities as developing a Karate protocol for seniors.

Instructors can train Karate as they wish. When working with frail older adults, it is important to know how exercise could affect their health, and ensure that any programmes are safe. Unfortunately, there is no universal protocol on training older adults and the data and news reported in the review could help to develop some guidelines for senior Karate athletes.

Considering the increasing ageing population, it is reasonable to suppose that probably always more seniors will approach Karate and martial arts. This might be seen as a problem for Karate instructors or Karate federations as there is no special protocol for special populations and specifically for older adults, but at the same time it is an opportunity for academic research to develop new links and new perspectives.

This literary review wants to be the first step in this direction, analysing the number and results of

previous studies related to Karate and the elderly. At the same time, the review could be very useful for the public, as both “Karate aficionados” or people interested in joining the martial art, will be informed about the benefits or possible risks of joining a Karate class in later life.

Reasons for participation in older Karatekas / martial artists

Because of the lack of dedicated research and the size of the field, strategic research martial arts research is quite a recent phenomenon¹³³. Twemlow et al. Reviewed previous research and suggested much of the attraction of martial arts stems from ritual performances which symbolically assist the individual to deal with existential questions, such as mortality, the quest for control, mystery, the hunt for power, and the search for identity¹⁴⁸. Other studies indicated that reasons for studying martial arts include self-discipline, self-defence, an outlet for aggression, physical exercise, social support, development of self-esteem, self-confidence, and power and mastery over unusual skills¹⁴⁸.

Some authors believe that an interest in the martial arts may be motivated by magical wishes and wishes for power, as suggested by the high interest in Karate in contemporary culture, and in film in particular. The martial arts movies might have played an important role in attracting people to the martial arts schools, but it would have not been enough, alone, to sustain student involvement over the long term¹⁴⁸. In fact, other authors show that among Karate practitioners, 66% of the subjects chose “Karatedō as a way of life” as their most important motive, 20% chose “athletic success”, and 12% chose health motives¹⁴⁸.

The study does not clarify the age of the athletes over 30 but it is possible to note a trend and that with increasing age, motivations to take part in martial arts as other physical activities change. The interest in understanding why people join martial arts increased among the German committee for martial arts

studies that launched the strategic research project Why martial arts? (WMA), interviewing Karate athletes and discovering 538 fascination or motivational categories for adults and 100 for children¹³³.

It is clear that there is not one definitive answer to why people and more specifically older adults join martial arts, and that the motivations seem to change according to age and cultural background. Nevertheless, it is worth considering that Twemlow et al., suggest that martial arts students could be identified by the three following 'perceived needs 'physical and recreational'; 'intellectual and emotional', and 'integrated self-transcendent' needs¹⁴⁸.

This theory fits in some way with Maslow's, who classified peoples' needs in a hierarchy. People start to satisfy their level of needs from the bottom to the top. People are able to satisfy the next level of needs only when they have satisfied all the needs of the previous one, and Maslow addresses the "transcendence needs": helping others to achieve self-actualization, at the last step of the pyramid⁹⁸.

One maybe could consider an implicit correlation between age and the steps of Maslow's pyramid, as the older we get, more are the needs we need to satisfy. In this sense, the link between Maslow and the study of Twemlow might suggest that the motivation for older adults to take part in martial arts or maybe physical activity, in general, should be searched in something other than physical fitness or health purposes, something more transcendent. Anyway, more specific studies need to be developed to understand why older adults join martial arts.

Critique of previous research and scope for improvement

One of the main limitations of studies included in this review is that the authors of previous studies have mainly generalised the word “Karate”. In fact, in the sport of Karate, there are several styles of Karate¹³⁴ and each style includes Kata and Kumite training, which may change according to the style and the kata or Kumite goal. Simply stating that participants engaged in Karate training may not provide sufficient details for the readers to understand what exercises have been performed, what Karate style has been adopted and the intensity of the training and consequently making any replication of the study impossible.

This has been previously noticed by Zetaruk et al., who claim how previous studies have often failed to identify either the specific style of martial arts, simply calling it “Karate”, or they have grouped several different styles together as one sport¹⁴⁹. Two authors have been more specific trying to give a description of the Karate training. Jansen states that the Karate training was developed according to the guidelines of the German-Karate-Federation, dkv¹²⁸.

Ludivine et al. add that “the adapted Karate training session involved 15 minutes of warm-up exercise, one hour of training, revision of past acquired skills, discovery, learning, and integration of new elements, with 15 minutes of stretching and cooling down. Training content, developed for the elderly by an expert teacher (third dan), was provided by four different teachers, according to a standardised protocol”¹²⁹.

These descriptions of Karate training interventions are unsatisfactory for several reasons. For example, what were the Karate exercises and the protocol used during the training are not clear as it is not clear how the training is developed on the DVK guidelines. This makes it very hard to try to replicate the study and compare the results. During the review, the author encountered one more problem: most of the papers

talking about Karate were focused on cultural perspectives, technical skills and injuries. Not many previous researches have focused on the correlation between health and Karate and even less papers have focused on older amateurs. The majority of research was for younger adults and for skilled athletes.

This is understandable considering the only recent interest of science in adapted physical activities, martial arts and in the recent problem of the ageing population. Therefore, the authors invite the readers to be very careful when they encounter the word Karate during publications and to consider that the Karate used for research might not be the same used in another and this can explain the possible different results. In fact, even in the same Karate styles there is no one official training protocol but only guidelines that change from federation to federation and that is up to the instructor to follow or not.

If this is not a big problem when we talk about Karate as a sport, it might be when trying to involve Karate as an adapted exercise in the clinical field.

Rationale and aims

Living longer could represent many advantages for our society such as having people to pursue new activities such as further education, a new career or long-neglected passion or help families and communities³⁰. Yet the extent of these opportunities and contributions depends heavily on the individual's health³⁰. Unhealthy ageing population growth is financially draining for public health care globally and many had to push back the age for eligibility of pensions and retirement benefits¹⁵⁰. Over the next 10 years, the ageing of the baby boom generation will yield an increase of nearly 236 million people aged 65 and older throughout the world¹⁵⁰.

Physical activity and structured exercise are currently considered essential to promote a healthier ageing^{55,56}. Unfortunately, despite the interest of the local authorities to develop physical activity

programs to improve health in the elderly, few subjects take part in these initiatives^{5,60}. An exception seems to be represented by martial arts⁶¹. One of the most popular practised martial arts is Karate¹³⁶. Previous findings have described associations between Karate and several health benefits mostly in young and middle age subjects, leaving unexplored the possible health benefits for later life.

Informed by this review of the literature, this thesis had four main aims:

1. TO UNDERSRTAKE SCOPING REVIEWTo investigate the interest of older adults in martial arts, specifically in Karate.
2. TO UNDERTAKE QUALITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE EXPERIENCE OF OLD KARATE COMPETITORSTo explore possible benefits of the practice of Karate on health and well-being in an older population.
3. UNDERTAKE ASSESSMENTS OF THE ROLE OF KARATE AND AGING ON SELF ESTEEM AND COPINGTo review previous issues related to Karate research.
4. TO ASSESS THE FEASIBILITY OF A REMOTE DELIVERED KARATE PROTOCOL FOR OLDER ADULTSTo promote the development of a unique adapted Karate protocol to promote health in an older population.

As a result of these aims, this thesis had three hypotheses:

1. Adapted Karate practice would be associated with greater health and quality of life in the elderly.
2. Adapted Karate would be tested as a possible new activity to promote active ageing, even online, during pandemics such as Covid-19.

3. Karate would be effective in improving levels of self-esteem and coping in elderly.

The aim of this review was to identify possible benefits on health in older adults from the practice of martial arts, specifically from the practice of Karate.

Previous findings have analysed possible correlations between Karate and several health benefits in different age-groups, anyway most authors focused on young and middle age subjects.

Results anyway show that the practice of martial arts such as Karate not only brings some health benefits for the practitioners, at any age, but it seems to fit better with the needs of the elderly population, compared to the actual proposed physical activity interventions¹³⁶.

Thus, it seems necessary to develop more studies to understand if Karate can be properly adapted to older adults and can be involved in public health initiatives to promote healthy ageing. It is also necessary to identify a common and unique adapted Karate protocol to help instructors using the same exercises when working with special populations.

Chapter II: Scoping Review – Health Benefits of Karate

Introduction

Recently, the number of people practising Karate in the world was estimated to be in excess of 50 million making it one of the most popular forms of martial arts worldwide¹³⁶. However, despite this widespread interest in Karate, scientific interest has been lacking in the literature. Moreover, there is a widespread assumption that Karate has similar benefits as has been reported for other martial arts¹³⁷ however there has been a little specific examination of the health benefits (or otherwise) of its practice. For example, in the systematic review noted earlier¹³⁷ only 3 of the 28 included studies examined Karate. Similarly, a more recent review also included 28 studies, 5 of which examined Karate practice¹²⁰.

Given the considerable number of individuals engaged in Karate, there is a need to summarise the available literature regarding the effects of its practice on individuals' health and well-being. However, given the relatively small numbers of studies included in the previous reviews^{120,137}, it is likely that the available literature is diverse and covers a range of broad topics with few areas of nuanced investigation. Therefore, a scoping review is considered as the most appropriate method of summarising the available literature¹⁵³. Scoping reviews use similar methods to systematic reviews in that they aim to use rigorous and transparent methods to identify literature and minimise bias¹⁵⁴. However, while systematic reviews attempt to answer a single, focussed research question, scoping reviews are best used to map a diverse body of literature, including a wide range of study designs and aims, and attempt to summarise the themes and findings without critically appraising each study or synthesising evidence¹⁵⁵. The main benefits of scoping reviews, therefore, are that they allow researchers to assess the current standing of a less mature research topic, while also identifying areas in which research is absent and future scholars might best

focus their efforts¹⁵⁵. Using these definitions, therefore, the aim of this study was to perform a scoping review of the available evidence regarding evidence for health benefits of Karate participation.

Methods

The methodology utilised for this scoping review is based on the scoping review framework outlined by Arksey and O'malley¹⁵³. This framework includes five key stages: (1) identifying the research question, (2) identifying relevant studies (3) study selection (4) charting the data and (5) collating, summarising and reporting the results¹⁵³.

Research question

This review was guided by a primary research question “*is Karate able to affect health and quality of life in the general population?*”, and in line with the framework being used, aimed to map the literature on this topic to identify key themes, gaps in the literature, and to identify types of evidence that might inform practice and policy making¹⁵³.

Search strategy

The search strategy involved three databases (PubMed, SPORTDiscus, and CINAHL) and the following keywords: Karate and health; Karate Shotokan and health; Karate Kyokushin and health; Karate Goju-Ryu and health; Karate Wado-Ryu and health; Karate Shito-Ryu and health; Karate, quality of life, well-being, health-related quality of life; Karate mental health. In addition, authors reviewed reference lists of included studies in order to identify other literature which may not have been identified from the primary search.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

To be included in this scoping review, studies had to include participants who were explicitly engaged in Karate training only and had to report a relevant health-related outcome. There were no restrictions on

the age or gender of study participants nor on the style of Karate performed. Studies of general martial arts, martial arts other than Karate, or where data from Karate performers were not presented separately to that of other martial artists were excluded.

Study selection and citation management

Results of database searches were imported into reference management software (Zotero, Fairfax, VA, USA). Once imported, duplicates were removed, and articles underwent assessment by each author for inclusion based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Studies underwent initial evaluation via assessment of the title and abstract. Full versions of studies that remained in scope for inclusion after this initial review were obtained and assessed for suitability. Those not suitable were removed with the reason noted.

Data extraction

To chart the data, the authors used a descriptive-analytical method within the narrative tradition, which involves applying a common analytical framework to all the primary research reports and collecting standard information on each study, consequently, data extraction included: bibliographic information, type of study, study aims, population investigated, sample size, relevant methodological information, health-related outcomes measures and their results. After data extraction, full versions of papers included in the review were read and coded to identify the main areas to which outcomes for each paper could be ascribed in a manner to qualitative thematic synthesis¹⁵⁶. Subsequently, papers were grouped into specific themes in which papers with outcomes in similar areas could be grouped¹⁵³

Results

Search strategy

The search strategy resulted in a total of 2600 hits from the three databases (figure 2). Once screened for duplicates, 1072 records remained. Subsequently, results were evaluated by title and abstract to remove those which failed to meet the inclusion criteria, resulting in the removal of a further 912 studies. For each of the remaining 160 studies, full versions of each paper were assessed to determine if it should be excluded, with the reason noted. After removing 138 papers for reasons including; being in languages other than English, being focused on general martial arts, or being focussed on cultural, philosophical or technical aspects of Karate, the authors identified a total of 21 papers meeting the inclusion criteria. Included studies underwent thematic synthesis¹⁵⁶ in order to identify studies which evaluated similar themes. In total there were 7 themes identified; musculoskeletal health^{157,158}, cardiovascular health^{142,159}, balance^{129,141} metabolic response^{143,160-162}, neurophysiology^{139,140,144,163-167}, psychology and behaviour^{129,168-171}, and injury^{167,172}. The topic of injury, outlined as one of the topics emerged from the scoping review, will not be analysed in this review because previously very well developed by Tomas et al. In the paper “injuries in Karate: systematic review”¹⁷³

*Figure 2 Schematic flow diagram describing exclusions of potential studies and final number of studies.
(RCT, randomised control trial; UCT, uncontrolled trial)*

The following table summarises the articles selected from the databases using the following keywords: Karate and health; Karate Shotokan and health; Karate Kyokushin and health; Karate Goju-Ryu and health; Karate Wado-Ryu and health; Karate Shito-Ryu and health; Karate, quality of life, well-being, health-related quality of life; Karate mental health.

Table 3 Summary of selected papers

Authors	Year	Study type	Population	Aims	Measures	Results
Akinoglu et al.	2019	intervention	24.53±3.62	Analyse strength and balance performance in Karate athletes with deafness	IsoMed 2000 isokinetic device, stadiometer (SECA-Mod. 220, Seca GmbH & Co. KG., Hamburg, Germany)	Stabilisation and equilibrium training improves muscle strength and balance performance in Karate athletes.
Kotarska et al	2019	observational	24.68 ± 8.24	To assess the intensity of health behaviours in martial artists	Health Behaviour Inventory (HBI) and survey	Karate athletes and Boxers have higher health behaviours
Lypowsky et al	2019	observational	18-65	investigate the connection between a sense of coherence and connectedness to nature with Karate athletes' objectives	Questionnaires	For women most important goal for the practice of Karate was well-being, while for men it was physical fitness
Chang et al.	2018	observational	31 to 41	To investigate involvement, perceived value, and leisure benefits of Karate participants	(1) involvement scale; (2) perceived value scale; (3) leisure benefits scale; (4) recommendation intention scale; and (5) personal basic data	athletes are confident to testify the leisure and psychological benefits of Karate

Quinzi et al.	2018	observational	unclear	Karate training develops in the upper limbs some specific neuromuscular adaptation	Maximal elbow flexion and extension. Measurement of the torque were taken using a dynamometer chair	The Karate group demonstrated higher peak torque and higher muscular fibre conduction velocity
Monda et al.	2017	observational	athletes 24.9 ± 4.9 , non-athletes 26.2 ± 4.5	Comparing resting motor threshold (rMT) and corticospinal response (MEP) in Karate practitioners and control group	Electromyography (EMG)	Karate can improve cortical excitability
Ito et al.	2016	observational	average 12,6	Analyse relationship between martial arts and Bone Mineral Density	DEXA	Judo and Karate athletes have higher BMD than control groups
Witte et al.	2016	intervention	average 70	to investigate possible effects of Karate training on older adults' cognitive function	DemTect test, the rod test, the DT Determination Test Version S11 and the Test of Divided Attention	improvement in motor reactivity, stress tolerance, and divided attention only after the 5-month Karate training
Sales et al.	2016	observational	28.2 ± 6.7	to assess the effects of a single Contact Karate session on post-exercise Blood Pressure	systolic (SBP), diastolic (DBP), and mean arterial pressure (MAP)	Contact Karate sessions can promote a decrease in BP

Jansen et al.	2017	intervention	52 to 81	Karate training and Mindfulness effects on emotional well-being and cognitive functioning in older adult	Questionnaires and hair cortisol	Improvement only in the Karate group
Moscatelli et al.	2016	observational	25 athletes 24.9 ± 4.9 and non-athletes 26.2 ± 4.5	Investigate neural activity in Karate athletes and non-athletes	EMG and Magstim Rapid Transcranial Magnetic Stimulator	Athletes showed faster Response Times, higher cortical excitability and also higher velocity.
Chaabène et al.	2012	review	unclear	To analyse the physical and physiological aspects of elite Karate athletes	Previous data review	Male Karate athletes resulted to have low body fat. Karate athletes resulted to have high bone mineral density and high VO2max
Tabben et al.	2013	observational	22.5 ± 1.2	To analyse heart rate (HR), pre and post [La-], and perceived exertion (RPE) in Karate athletes during competition	Anthropometric measurements, maximal tests and blood tests	International Karate competition elicited near-maximal cardiovascular responses and high [La-] concentrations.
Alesi et al.	2014	observational	9.05 ± 1.04	to explore the motor abilities and cognitive skills of children practising Karate	agility test, the standing board jump test and a cognitive test(BVN 5-11)	Karate children had higher scores in all the tests, compared to the control group

Benedini et al	2012	observational	21.9 ± 1.1	To analyse the effects of Karate and the glucose-insulin system	Blood samples	glucose and epinephrine concentrations increased more after Kumite than after kata.
Drozdowska et al.	2011	observational	25.64 ± 12.3	to assess the influence of regular Karate training on the skeletal status	Quantitative Ultra Sound method. DBM Sonic 1200 (IGEIA, Carpi, Italy)	Karate improves the skeletal status
Sbriccoli et al.	2010	observational	24.8 ± 1.0 athletes	investigating the neuromuscular response of knee flexor and extensor muscles in elite Karate and Karate amateurs	surface electromyograms (sEMG)	improved ability of elite Karateka to recruit fast MUs
			27.8 ± 1.0 amateurs			
Probst et al.	2007	observational	24.3 +/- 6.7 years	to compare lower body strength, flexibility and knee stability of Karate athletes against non Karate athletes	Eccentric isokinetic testing	Karate athletes may have demonstrated sport-specific adaptations in certain flexibility and strength measurements
Vera et al.	2018	observational		to examine the effects of Karate on several hormonal parameters	Blood samples	Karate practice is associated with a significant endocrine modulation
			18 to 55			
Manzaneque et al.	2018	observational	20 to 50	to clarify the effects that long-term Karate practice can exert over immune parameters	Blood samples	Karate athletes showed better value than non-athletes

Ludivine et al.	2010	intervention	Average 56	to identify the effects of an adapted Karate training program on QOL, depression, and motor skills in 50-year-old men	MOS 36-item Short Form Health Survey (SF36), BDI. <hr/> Motor functions were quantified by computerised testing	Regular long-term Karate practice had favourable effects on mood, perception of physical health, and improved performance on objective physical testing
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Main themes

Musculoskeletal health

Five studies reported on musculoskeletal health. Ito et al.¹⁵⁷ assessed the relationship between martial arts performance (judo, Karate, and kung-fu) and bone mineral density versus age-matched controls using dual x-ray absorptiometry (DEXA). They reported that Karate and judo practitioners exhibited increased BMD compared to kung fu athletes and non-martial arts practitioners. Moreover, this was site-specific with no differences in the lower limbs whereas arm BMD was significantly greater. This cross-sectional study was composed of 138 adolescents of both sexes from 11 to 14 years old. For adolescents engaged in martial arts, the following criteria were included: (i) aged between 11 and 17; (ii) a minimum of 3 months of previous involvement in the current martial art and (iii) the coach's permission. Adolescents practiced the following martial arts: Karate (9 girls and 5 boys [*Shotokan* style]), Judo (8 girls and 10 boys) and Kung-fu (1 girl and 15 boys [*sanda* style]). The control group was composed of 135 adolescents aged between 11 and 17. The selection criteria were: (i) aged between 11 and 17 and (ii) not engaged in regular physical activity/sport outside school). The control group was composed of 36 girls and 54 boys. Weekly training load was measured by means of a questionnaire filled in by the coach, in which the following questions about each athlete were asked: (i) the number of days per week and (ii) number of hours per days spent training. Weekly training load was calculated using the equation: number of days×hours per day (expressed in minutes/week). Time of previous engagement in the martial art was also reported by the coach (in months), as well as the use of any supplementation (weight loss or muscle mass-gain). The bone mineral density (in g/cm²) in different body regions (i) whole body BMD, (ii) BMD of the lower limbs, (iii) BMD of the upper limbs, (iv) BMD of the spine region, (v) BMD of the pelvis and (vi) BMD of the trunk) was analyzed using the Dual-Energy X-ray Absorptiometry (DEXA) technique. The study anyways shows some limitations: the cross-sectional design in which there is an absence of causality should be considered. Moreover, the absence of nutritional factors (e.g. calcium and vitamin D) and exposure to sunlight should be considered in future studies. All bone variables analyzed in the present study are strongly affected by biological

maturation. Finally, DXA does not provide measures of bone geometry, which could be useful in studies analyzing this issue.

Similarly, drozdowska et al.¹⁵⁸ investigated the effect of regular Karate training on hand BMD using quantitative ultrasound. They reported that both the duration and frequency of Karate participation were positively associated with measures of BMD in those who took up the sport later (from the age of 13–group 2) whereas no such association was seen in those who had been training from a young age. Probst et al.,¹³⁹ compared isokinetic muscle function, flexibility and knee stability in experienced Karate participants with healthy controls. They reported that Karate athletes had greater hip flexion in the dominant leg. They also demonstrated greater concentric and eccentric peak torque at 60 degrees.sec⁻¹ in both the quadriceps and hamstrings and the hamstrings had a quicker time to peak torque. And shorter time to peak torque. Conversely, they did not demonstrate worse levels of knee stability. Overall the study suggested that Karate improved lower limb muscle function without increasing the risk of a knee injury. Sbriccoli et al.,¹⁶⁴ also assessed lower limb isokinetic function this time in elite Karate performers versus amateurs. They demonstrated that elite performers had higher isokinetic knee flexion torque at all isokinetic velocities when compared with amateurs as well as a higher conduction velocity during test performance. Six Elite karateka (age 24.8 ± 1.0years, stature 1.78 ± 0.03 m, body mass 73.8 ± 4.0 kg, BMI 23.1 ± 0.7 kg/m²) and six Amateurs (age 27.8 ± 1.0years, stature 1.80 ± 0.03 m, body mass 77.0 ± 3.6 kg, BMI 23.8 ± 1.6 kg/m²), all males, volunteered to participate in the study. Elite karateka participating in the study were athletes selected within the national karate team with a minimum of 15 years of karate practice. Amateurs were karate practitioners with between 5 and 10 years of practice. Elite athletes and Amateurs were first subjected to a series of isokinetic knee flexion\extensions (isokinetic task, ISOK). Then, In a separate session, all subjects were tested while performing a basic karate kick. Surface EMG

(sEMG) signals were recorded during the ISOK and the kick protocol using a portable wi-fi trans-mission EMG amplifier (BTS Pocket EMG, Italy). During the kick, in order to assess hip and knee angular velocities of the kicking leg, magnetic field angular rate and gravity sensors (MARG) (MTx, Xsens Motion Technologies, Enschede, The Netherlands) were placed on the sacrum (on S1 vertebra), on the latero-distal thigh (10 cm above the lateral epicondyle), and on the medial facet of the tibia (5 cm above the medial malleolus) of each subject. Knee flexion and extension torques were recorded using an dynamometric device (REV 9000, Technogym, Italy). After a 5-min warm up, subjects were asked to perform maximal voluntary isometric knee flexion and extensions (three attempts, 5 s each). The attempts were spaced by a 3-min. interval. After a convenient rest period, all subjects performed three sets of maximal concentric knee flexion–extensions at different angular velocities, namely 30°, 90°, 180°, 270°, 340°, and 400°/s. After 2 weeks, Elite karateka and Amateurs were asked to perform a front kick (FK). In order to reproduce the action performed during a Kumite combat, subjects were asked to wait for a visual trigger to start the (FK). The research is a magnificent example of how to evaluate lower limb isokinetic functions, on the other hand, one might consider that the number of participants is relatively small and that leaves the reader to think if results were different if elite karate athletes were compared to elite athletes of another sport.

Similarly, Quinzi et al.¹⁴⁰ also used isokinetic techniques to assess muscle coordination this time of the upper arms. They assessed the isokinetic performance of the biceps brachii and triceps in trained Karate participants versus controls. Torque and surface electromyograms (sEMG) of Biceps Brachii Caput Longum (BB) and Triceps Brachii Lateral Head (TB) were recorded in eight karate practitioners (KA) and eight age-matched sedentary individuals (CO) during isokinetic elbow flexion–extensions (0–240°/s⁻¹). BB and TB sEMG amplitude (Root Mean Square - RMS) and frequency

(Median Frequency – MDF) were computed during agonist and antagonist activity. Moreover, muscle fibre conduction velocity (MFCV) of the BB was computed. They demonstrated that the Karate group had similar EMG characteristics, but quicker muscle fibre conduction velocity and greater peak torque in both muscles investigated.

Balance

Two studies assessed Karate and balance. Akinoğlu et al.¹⁴¹ undertook a randomised controlled trial (RCT) to assess the effect of 6 weeks of either isokinetic stabilisation or equilibrium training on the hip flexor and extensor muscular strength and balance performance in hearing impaired Karate athletes. Both groups demonstrated significant improvements in both balance and hip strength showing that stabilisation and equilibrium training have helped the Karate athletes with deafness to improve their muscle strength and balance performance¹⁴¹. The study involved 20 (11 males and 9 females) athletes of national Olympic level sports goalball team. The inclusion criteria for the study included not having any systemic problem or any health problem except their impairment and having cooperation for testing. Isokinetic muscular strength was assessed by IsoMed 2000 (D. & R. Ferstl GmbH, Hemau, Germany) device. Prior to the test, the athletes did structured warm-up protocol for 10 min. Considering every athletes' anthropometric feature, the isokinetic device's setting was made following the warming. The assessment protocol included five repeats of the knee flexion/extension movement at 90°/sec for familiarization and comprehension of device mechanism, 5 repeats of maximal knee flexion/extension movement at 60°/sec and 15 repeats of maximal knee flexion/extension movement at 240°/sec velocity, the sequence of the angular velocity is changed depending on their randomization. Athletes rested for 1 min between each angular velocity. The assessments were made bilaterally for each joint. First the dominant side was assessed and 3 min later the nondominant side was assessed. The dominant lower limb was defined by the athlete as the leg that was predominantly

used to kick the ball (Chiou et al., 2013). The knee flexion and extension peak torque (PT), % of flexion/extension PT ratio, % of dominant/nondominant PT differences at 60°/sec and 240°/sec velocities were noted (Akinoğlu and Kocahan, 2017). Balance assessment was carried out with Human Body Equilibrium 360 (HUBER 360, LPG Systems, Middx, France). As balance tests, stability tests were evaluated how much a person can hold his position during 50 sec. Single leg balance tests were also performed. All the data obtained from the measurements of athletes were analyzed with IBM SPSS Statistics ver. 22.0 (IBM Co., Armonk, NY, USA). Before analyzing the data, the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was done to determine if the data was normally distributed or not. The variables were calculated as means± standard deviation. The statistical significance was set at $P<0.05$. Nevertheless, it is important to mconsider that there was control group to compare.

Marie-ludivine¹²⁹ also assessed the effect of adapted Karate training on balance in middle-aged adults during a prospective 1-year observational study. Their intervention included a 90 min adapted Karate session three times per week for the duration of the study and reported improved balance during eyes closed postural sway assessment. The study involved fifteen 50-year-old men were enrolled in a one-year prospective experiment. Participants practiced adapted karate training for 90 minutes three times a week. Testing sessions, involving completion of the MOS 36-item Short Form Health Survey (SF36) and Beck Depression Inventory, as well as motor and effort evaluation, were done at baseline, and six and 12 months. To adapt the Karate training, the authors removed antiphysiologic postures and techniques, adapted progression (eg, training at a slow cadence, a push-attack approach), and optimized coaching according to the ability of each trainee. Each session involved 15 minutes of warmup exercise, one hour of training, revision of past acquired skills, discovery, learning, and integration of new elements, with 15 minutes of stretching and cooling down. Training content, developed for the elderly by an expert teacher (third Dan), was provided by four different teachers, according to a standardized protocol. The authors reported anyway the following limitations: the

size and nature of the sample (ie, males only) and the lack of a comparison group (without intervention). Therefore, these results should be considered as encouraging preliminary data, and the starting point of a new 18-month intervention study in a larger sample of population.

Cardiovascular health

Two studies investigated the effects of Karate on cardiovascular health. Magalhaes sales et al.,¹⁴² investigated the effect of Karate performance on blood pressure (BP) responses. They reported that a single session of contact Karate is able to increase post-exercise hypotension and results and may be effective in reducing blood pressure at least for 60 minutes after the training. The study included thirty-two male Contact Karate (CK) athletes volunteered (28.2 ± 6.7 years; 77.0 ± 5.7 kg; and 176.0 ± 4.7 cm) and underwent one CK session (50 minutes) and a control session in which no exercise was performed and the individuals remain seated during the whole time. BP was measured during rest (before sessions), as well as on the 15th, 30th, 45th, and 60th minutes of the post-exercise recovery. The CK session was divided in four stages: 1) volunteers performed a warm-up that consisted of calisthenics and relaxed punching and front-kicking (without tension); 2) CK techniques were conducted (punching and kicking) with the volunteers pairing with a colleague; 3 a CK fight (Kumite) was performed, with the volunteers alternating among each other; and 4, the 60 minutes post-exercise recovery period, in which BP was measured at each 15 minutes. This interesting study is the only, according the authors, to analyse BP in CK, which makes it difficult to compare with other studies. Another limitation is the small sample size and the missing of a deep description of the performed karate techniques.

Tabben et al.,¹⁵⁹ assessed different methods of assessing training loads during Karate competitions and assessed her responses during bouts. The authors identified that Karate bouts resulted in near maximal peak heart rate(HR) and required training protocols that mimicked this exercise intensity. The research included eleven karatekas but only data from seven athletes who completed three matches in an international tournament were used (four men and three women). The duration of combat was 3 min for men and 2 min for women, with 33.6 ± 7.6 min for the first interval period (match 1–2) and 14.5 ± 3.1 min for the second interval period (match 2–3). HR was continuously recorded during each combat. Blood lactate [La^-] and (RPE) were measured just before the first match and immediately after each match. The big limitation of this study is that the data was taken only from seven karate athletes (four male and three female). Thus, future investigations using larger samples and athletes with other characteristics is necessary to confirm the results of the study.

Metabolic effects

Tabben et al.,¹⁵⁹ assessed metabolic responses during competitive Karate bouts, reporting that practitioners frequently lactate concentrations in excess of 8mmol.l^{-1} immediately following a bout. Chaabène et al. Have also assessed Karate athletes' metabolic response, proving the athletes' higher vo_2max when compared to age-matched controls¹⁴³. This paper is a review that was performed using the US National Library of Medicine (PubMed), Web of Science, SPORTDiscus and Google Scholar databases. The literature search period used was from January 1980 to December 2011. The specific keywords were the following: 'karate', 'karate AND performance', 'karate AND physical fitness', 'karate AND anthropometric characteristics', 'karate AND aerobic energy system', 'karate AND anaerobic energy system', 'karate AND muscular power' and 'karate AND muscular strength'. Limitations of the paper are that the majority of results were based on male athletes and the number of papers included was limited, because of the lack of research in Karate.

Benedini et al.,¹⁶⁰ investigated the effects of a session of Karate practice on the glucose-insulin system pre- and post either combat (Kumite) or Kata training in a cohort of ten national and international Karate competitors. They report that indicate glucose and catecholamine concentration was elevated following both forms of training, and that Kumite resulted in larger increases in norepinephrine that occurred following kata. The study involved Ten healthy individuals (6M/4F; BMI: $22.1 \pm 0.7 \text{ kg/m}^2$; 21.9 ± 1.1 years, mean \pm SE) who practice karate in national or international competitions were enrolled. All participants completed two experimental trials in a randomised-crossover fashion. A basal blood sample was collected from each athlete to assess plasma glucose, insulin, cortisol, testosterone and catecholamines, before karate training session. In two separate days, another blood sample was collected from each participants after 3 min of real fighting (*kumite*) and 3 min of ritualized simulation of combat (*kata*). Limitations of the study are to be noted in the fact that it included only a small sample of elite athletes and these results do not apply for general population and amateurs.

Vera et al.,¹⁶¹ examined the effects of Karate on resting hormonal parameters of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal and hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axes in long-time practitioners versus non-Karate performer controls. They found that the Karate group had similar levels of adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ATCH) and dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA), thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) and free triiodothyronine (t3) they had significantly lower levels of cortisol and free thyroxine (t4). Twenty-two healthy volunteer subjects (12 experimental and 10 controls) participated in the study. Experimental subjects were karate players with a minimum of 3 years of practice in this discipline. Blood samples for the quantification of hormonal parameters were taken in both groups. The Mann-Whitney *U* test was performed for each variable in order to analyze the differences between groups. This research finds limitations in the small sample size, in the fact that endocrine parameters were assessed only once and that Karate was not compared to other activities of the same intensity.

Finally, Manzanque et al.,¹⁶² examined the effects of long-term Karate practice on immune parameters. They assessed resting levels of leukocytes, neutrophils, monocytes, eosinophils, basophils, lymphocytes, igg, iga, and igm in fifteen Karate participants with a minimum of 3-years training with sedentary controls. The regular Karate group demonstrated superior markers of immune function with increased levels of total leukocytes, monocytes, and lymphocytes, and greater serum concentrations of igg and igm. The study involved 15 long-term karate practitioners (12 with black belt and 3 with brown belt), and 12 ordinary subjects with no previous experience of karate or other martial arts as control group. All subjects had the same characteristics (age, height, weight, and trait anxiety). The Karate training in the experimental group typically entailed two to three lessons a week, with a duration of about one hour each. Experimental subjects had been following this routine for a minimum of 3 years. Karate practice, which is normally preceded by a brief heating, traditionally consists of “kata” (i.e., a prearranged solo fighting sequence), combat drills (i.e., short fighting techniques practiced with a partner), and “kumite” (i.e., a sparring practice involving two partners). Blood samples were then collected and analysed according standard laboratory techniques. The small number of subjects in the sample as well as measuring immune parameters at one time-point only throughout the study may be considered, to a certain extent, a limitation of its overall results.

Neurophysiology

Monda et al.,¹⁶³ investigated the effect of Karate participation on muscle coordination, using transcranial magnetic stimulation (TCMS). When compared to non-Karate controls, Karate participants exhibited lower motor threshold, shorter mep latency, and higher mep amplitude compared to non-athletes. Taken together the authors suggest long-term training results in the adaptation of excitability of the corticospinal system. The authors recruited 25 right-handed young karate athletes and 25 matched non-athletes. TMS was applied to primary motor cortex (M1). Motor evoked potential (MEP) were recorded by two electrodes placed above

the first dorsal interosseous (FDI) muscle. We considered MEP latencies and amplitudes at rMT, 110% of rMT, and 120% of rMT. Bigger samples will be needed to confirm the results.

Similarly, Moscatelli et al.,¹⁶⁵ extended this work by further demonstrating that the alterations in the corticospinal system were negatively correlated with reaction time performance in a similar group of young Karate adults. The research included twenty-five male karate athletes (24.9 ± 4.9 years) and 25 matched non-athletes (26.2 ± 4.5 years). Using TMS, the authors investigated cortico-spinal system excitability. The karate athletes were all black belts, regularly competing at national and international levels and training at least five 2-h sessions week for the previous 5 years. The controls declared to be not engaged in any competitive or amateur sports. Subjects were asked not to perform any physical activity in the 2 days before the recordings.

Participants seated in comfortable armchair, in a quiet room, with their right hand stabilized and supported during the exam with the elbow positioned at 90° flexion, to have the same muscle length during electromyography (EMG) recording. The motor cortex excitability was evaluated using a 70-mm figure-of-eight coil connected to a Magstim Rapid2 (maximum output 2.2 T) Transcranial Magnetic Stimulator (The Magstim Company Ltd, UK), placed over the left motor cortex. A mechanical arm maintained the handle of the coil tangential to the scalp with the handle pointing backward at 45° away from the mid line while delivering the stimulus. The location of the stimulation was identified on each subject's scalp using the SofTaxis navigator system. The subjects were instructed to respond as quickly as possible to a visual stimulus. The analyzed output variable is mean reaction response time. One limitation of the study is that the karate athletes were compared to non-athletes. Therefore the results might be found in other athletes practicing other sports and not be related to practice of Karate per se.

Witte et al.,¹⁶⁶ investigated possible effects of Karate training on older adults' cognitive functions. They randomised 89 individuals aged over 63 yrs into either a Karate training group, a general fitness training

group or a control group. Both intervention groups underwent regular training twice per week, led either by a Karate expert or a fitness trainer. All participants underwent a cognitive test battery after 5 months, while the Karate group underwent a second round of testing after 10 months. The authors report that at the 5-month follow-up, only the Karate training group exhibited improvements in motor reactivity, stress tolerance, and divided attention. Further improvements in these measures were noted at the 10-month follow-up. Alesi et al.,¹⁴⁴ compared the motor abilities and cognitive skills of children who regularly (3 times a week) practised Karate with age-matched sedentary controls. They found that children attending Karate demonstrated higher measures of motor performance including sprint, agility and jump performance. Similarly, the children engaged in regular Karate practice also demonstrated better performance in cognitive tests of memory, attention, and executive function.

Psychology and behaviour

Five studies investigate how Karate affects physiological and behavioural aspects of athletes. Kotarska et al.,¹⁶⁸ examined the intensity of health behaviours in over 400 different martial arts performers. Using the health behaviour inventory questionnaire (HBIQ) they reported that the most intense health behaviours were evident in those performing Karate, boxers and mixed martial arts (MMA) athletes. They also reported that within all sports examined, daily practice was associated with greater intensity of health behaviours. The research embraced 441 people who practiced martial arts and combat sports. The respondents were at various sporting levels. The average age of the subjects was 24.68 ± 8.24 years. Men accounted for 52.6% of the respondents. This study used data on age, sex, place of residence, education, type of work and financial situation as well as information on sporting disciplines, sporting experience, and weekly exercise time. The results obtained with the help of HBI and its categories were referred to these variables. The majority were unmarried (72.5%). Among the subjects, 52.8% still studied, but 14.5% of those who were in schools also worked. 40.2% were employed (25.2% did mental and 15% physical work), 3.6% ran their own businesses. Subjects who were

between jobs and those who chose not to work constituted 3.4%. The standardized health behavior inventory (HBI) was used to assess health behaviors and their intensity. The limitation of this paper might be that too many variables have been considered so that is not easy to understand if the health behaviours are related to the sport or to the general quality of life of the individuals. For example, results might change if the test was delivered in another country with different health habits.

Lipowski et al.,¹⁶⁹ investigated the association between Karate participation and psychological coherence and connectedness to nature. They investigated 127 athletes using the inventory of physical activity objectives (IPAO), the sense of coherence questionnaire, and the connectedness to nature scale. Results reveal that for female practitioners, the most important goal was well-being, while for men it is physical fitness, however, in both sexes connectedness to nature was highest in those whose main motivation was to improve physical fitness. The main limitation of the current study concerns its cross-sectional nature and the fact that researched relationships cannot indicate causality.

Chang et al.,¹⁷⁰ investigated the effects of Karate involvement, perceived value, and leisure benefits on Karate participants' recommendation intentions. Using an online questionnaire, they reported that those engaged in Karate are willing to recommend Karate engagement to others, however, this appeared to be driven predominantly by their intrinsic attraction to the sport and less so by any perceived improvements in psychological or physiological health benefits. The questionnaire contained five parts: (1) involvement scale; (2) perceived value scale; (3) leisure benefits scale; (4) recommendation intention scale; and (5) personal basic data investigation. Research variables of the scales were scored with Likert's five-point scale, including: (1) extremely disagree; (2) disagree; (3) slightly agree; (4) agree; and (5) extremely agree, which are orderly given the scores of 1 to 5. The higher scores represent the higher identification of participants. The paper is definitely important for the development of martial arts in the literature, but it has some limitations. Main limitations of this study are the use of not strongly validated questionnaires and the lack of in depth interviews.

Jansen et al.,¹⁷¹ examined the effects of Karate on measures of mental health in older adults. They randomised fifty-five participants to either 8-weeks of Karate training or a mindfulness-based stress reduction intervention or a control group. They reported that only the Karate group demonstrated improvements in anxiety measured with the hospital anxiety and depression scale (hads) and mental health measured using the short form 12 (SF12) questionnaire. The present study has several limitations as the fairly small sample of healthy volunteers and the short time between pre- and postassessment that may have led to practice effects in the cognitive performance measures. Moreover, the postassessment immediately followed the last training session. Thus, the karate and the MBSR group participants may have been tired or at least in a different mood or physical state compared to the baseline assessment. Besides, the three groups differed in the relative number of males and females participating.

Finally, in addition to assessing the effect of Karate on balance (reported above), Marie-Ludivine et al.,¹²⁹ also investigates the effects of adapted Karate training on the quality of life for middle-aged men. They used a 1-year prospective follow-up study with participants taking part in a 90-minute Karate training session three times per week. They found that participation in Karate resulted in reduced Beck Depression Inventory scores, and improved perception of their physical but not mental health assessed using the Short Form 36 inventory. Limitations of this paper have been discussed in the previous paragraph.

Discussion

The main aim of this review was to assess the available literature and to map the health-related themes which have been investigated in respect of Karate participation. This analysis found that 7 themes were represented in the literature; musculoskeletal health, cardiovascular health, balanced metabolic effects, neurophysiology, psychology and behaviour, and injury. However, despite the breadth of studies

included in this scoping review, there remains significant limitations in respect of the quality and generalizability of the available evidence.

The beneficial effects of regular participation in exercise or sporting activities are well recognised. In the musculoskeletal system, these include improvements in bone density and the prevention of osteoporosis^{174,175} and improved indices of muscle strength and power¹⁷⁶. From the available data, it appears that Karate participation results in similar adaptations. It is therefore not surprising that both studies which assessed bone mineral density both reported improvements that were site and training status specific^{138,158} as similar changes, both in terms of bone density and site specificity have been reported in other sports¹⁷⁷. Consequently, it seems likely that Karate results in similar improvements in bone health as other high-impact sports. Indeed, given that osteoporosis is one of the major challenges for public health and that peak bone mass achieved at young age is the predictor of later life osteoporosis risk¹⁷⁸, Karate could have a role in supporting BMD in both young and older female participants. Similar arguments can be made in terms of muscle strength since all three studies^{139,140,164} reported improvements in isokinetic measures of muscle strength. Of particular interest is that all three studies also reported increases in muscle conduction velocity indicating that Karate performance results in adaptation across the entire neuromuscular system. Similar adaptations have recently been reported following short-term resistance training¹⁷⁹, again suggesting that Karate participation results in similar beneficial adaptations as other forms of sport participation.

Many martial arts include the performance of katas, slower deliberate body movements in which the individual practices the body positions, movements, and weight transfer required to perform key movements¹⁵². In particular, the use of these slow, deliberate movements has been investigated as a method of improving balance in a variety of populations, most notably, there is a large body of evidence

regarding the effects of the martial art Tai Chi¹⁸⁰. Karate also includes a focus on katas to improve balance, movement and technical ability. However, the effectiveness of Karate katas to improve balance has received relatively little attention with the current review finding only three studies which assessed balance. However, of those only one prospectively assessed the ability of Karate performance to improve balance¹²⁹, reporting an improvement when the balance was assessed using postural sway with eyes closed. The finding that balance is unaffected when assessed with eyes open but improved with eyes closed is similar to findings reported in Tai Chi. For example, Wong et al.,¹⁸¹ reported similar reductions in postural sway velocity in Tai Chi practitioners when assessed using an eyes-closed protocol. While the balance improvement reported following Karate training by Marie-Ludvine¹²⁹ is promising, far more research is necessary before Karate training can be promoted as an effective method of improving balance.

The cardiovascular benefits of regular exercise are well known and form the basis of most governmental advice to reduce the risks of cardiovascular disease¹⁸². Clearly, martial arts in general represent one form of physical activity in which individuals might engage in order to meet the suggested amounts of physical activity^{120,137}. Given the high profile of physical activity in health promotion, the lack of studies examining the effectiveness of Karate training to improve measures of cardiovascular health is surprising. Only two studies in the present review reported on outcomes related to cardiovascular health. As with balance research, the findings are promising. Karate competition requires near-maximal heart rates¹⁵⁹ and results in a transient reduction in blood pressure¹⁴². Findings that are similar to post-exertional hypotension were reported following other forms of exercise¹⁸³ and the heart rates generated in high-intensity interval training¹⁸⁴ however, again these findings while promising are limited in scope, and much more work is needed to better evaluate the ability of Karate to reduce cardiovascular risk.

Metabolic responses contribute to the maintenance of homeostasis in the body through impact on a multitude of physiological systems^{185,186}. Benedini et al.¹⁶⁰ found that Karate results in substantial increases in sympathetic drive which is more pronounced in combat training compared to kata practice. The effects of Karate on metabolism are also confirmed by other authors that show how regular Karate practice is associated with decreased blood levels of cortisol and thyroid hormones¹⁶¹ at rest and an increase of cortisol during competition¹⁸⁷. Karate training, compared to other martial arts, seems to improve the immune system¹⁶².

There is evidence that Karate may enhance neurological function with a series of studies demonstrating that long-term training results improved motor control which in turn are correlated with the improved reaction time performance seen in well-trained Karate participants^{163,165}. Others have also a sport-specific adaptation of neurological function, particularly when assessed using tcms¹⁸⁸ suggesting that Karate training results in similar neurological adaptation as reported in other sports. In addition, there has been interest in the use of exercise which includes complex motor skills to provide a neuroprotective effect which may translate to the improved cognitive function of physical function. For example, recently Narici et al.,¹⁸⁹ demonstrated that dance performance in older adults resulted in a greater neuroprotective effect than did usual aerobic and resistance training of the same intensity. Given that Karate requires encoding of complex motor skills which must also be performed semi-autonomously, it is possible that the neurological benefits identified may also be neuroprotective in advancing age, however, more specific investigation of this area is needed. The present review also found reasonable evidence that Karate participation improves cognitive function across a wide age range from children to older adults. However, while the evidence in older adults is stronger, including a prospective study with a 10-month follow up¹⁶⁶ the evidence of improvements in children is based on a single cross-sectional study.

Nevertheless, these findings warrant further investigation since a recent systematic review failed to find evidence to support a role of exercise in improving cognitive function in older adults¹⁹⁰

Martial arts are different to many sports in that alongside the teaching participants specific skills and manoeuvres related to the sport, teachings may also include philosophical, historical, and cultural aspects¹⁹¹. These additional aspects have meant that martial arts in general have been investigated as methods of influencing recalcitrant behaviours, often in difficult to reach groups^{192,193}. From the present study, there is some evidence that Karate may also be effective in modifying participants' attitudes and behaviours with one prospective studies and one randomised control trial reporting improvements in mental health. Previous work has indicated that exercise may be as effective as medical interventions for reducing depression¹⁹⁴, anxiety¹⁹⁵, and quality of life in a variety of populations^{196–198}, and the present review suggests that Karate is similarly effective as other forms of exercise.

Limitations

While the aim of a scoping review does not generally include a specific assessment of study quality, there are several limitations to a body of work comprising this review which should be noted. First, a large majority of studies included in the review were observational in nature. While such approaches are useful in hypothesis-generating, they may be more prone to bias, and cannot establish cause and effect¹⁹⁹. Therefore in many cases, it is not possible to say definitively that Karate participation was the reason for any differences identified. Similarly, most studies had a relatively small sample size, no studies provided a justification for the sample size used. Several studies compared Karate groups with sedentary individuals so it is unclear if the results are due to Karate per se or to a general physical activity^{140,144,163,165}. Similarly, some research is focused only on elite athletes¹⁶⁴, leaving an important

question regarding the adaptability of the results to the general population and amateurs. Consequently, these results should be considered as encouraging preliminary data, and the starting point of new intervention studies in a larger sample of population . In addition, apart from 4 studies^{142,160,166,171}, the description of the Karate training used by participants is poor and precludes effective replication. Given that there are over different styles of Karate and each style including Kata and Kumite training, which may change according to the style and the kata or Kumite goal¹³⁴, simply stating that participants engaged in Karate training may not provide sufficient detail. Finally, of the papers included, only three focussed on older adults^{129,166,171}, the issues of an ageing population, and the broad application of other forms of martial arts to improve physical function in older adults¹⁸¹, further investigation of Karate in this population is warranted.

Conclusions

Results confirm that Karate is effective as much as other physical exercises to improve cardiovascular health, psychological well-being, BMD, balance, neurological activity and in the promotion of healthy ageing. On the other hand, studies about Karate are relatively low in number and miss a technical perspective, leaving the final results under unclear lights. In such a complex sport as Karate, where there is a traditional and modern school, where there are 2 specialities as Kata and Kumite and different styles, each one with different training and technical structures, it seems necessary for future research to be very clear about the participants' training, as the final results may be related not to Karate in general but to the own Karate style or speciality. The outcomes of the review, anyway, should be taken into serious consideration by future research to move the attention from the most popular forms of martial arts, such as Tai Chi, to less popular ones, such as Karate, that seem to be even more effective in the promotion of healthy ageing because of their higher impact training. Nevertheless, the findings may inspire Karate

federations around the world to develop a common adapted Karate protocol for the development of health during the lifespan and to pay more attention to the needs of an always-growing senior population.

Chapter III: Dojo and martial arts: a social
community for physical activity and healthy
ageing

Introduction

The world's population is ageing fast, experiencing serious issues with falls and balance impairments in elderly populations¹. Increasing age is associated with a greater risk of functional loss and disability¹⁰, associated with greater public health care expenditure¹².to reduce the risk of several age-related chronic conditions, it is necessary to keep older adults physically active^{55,200,201} as sedentary lifestyle in the elderly is highly related to loneliness, which in turn is associated with an increased risk of frailty²⁰². This suggests a weak social involvement and loneliness in older adults, not only affects mental health but can also increase the risk of frailty and chronic disease. Furthermore, social and relational changes affect both the working (retirement, inactivity, sense of uselessness) and the family dimension (children physically distant and/or professionally involved), determining changes in relationships and networks, leaving older adults feeling more peripheral and alone, especially if sick and disabled²⁰³. To keep physically and socially active, physical activity is routinely prescribed, as it has been demonstrated to improve physical and mental health^{55,204}. However typically, fewer than half of older adults invited to join interventions take up the opportunity^{205,206} suggesting older adults are not motivated to be physically and socially involved²⁰⁷.

According to the literature, martial arts and combat sport exercises may help people become fitter, defend themselves, feel more relaxed and develop specific personal and cultural values²⁰⁸, with an increased participation of senior athletes⁹⁴. Authors found martial arts and combat sports promote an idea of self-cultivation among students that helps to develop three main areas: shared cultivation, social cultivation and ecological cultivation²⁰⁸. In addition to the primary health benefits of practising martial arts¹⁶⁶, other

factors may explain the popularity of martial arts. One aspect to consider is the ability of martial arts to improve empathy, helping practitioners to “really feel what another person is feeling or going to do”²⁰⁹. Spiritualism and empathy are important to highlight as they have been considered motivational support for physical activity and social involvement in the elderly^{96,98}. Even more, martial arts reward in some way the “wisdom of ageing”. In fact, experts are not allowed to achieve the grade of master, in Karate, if younger than 40 years of age, regardless of the results in competitions²¹⁰. Every Karate training session starts and ends saluting one's master and training companions²¹⁰.

Getting older is not only challenging for our bodies, but also for one's self-perception²¹¹. Levy's longitudinal study of 660 people 50 years and older showed that those with more positive self-perceptions of ageing lived 7.5 years longer than those with negative self-perceptions of ageing²¹². Stereotypes, prejudice, or discrimination against (but also in favour of) people because of their chronological age are defined as ageism²¹³. One of the common myths about ageing is that “older adults should take it easy and avoid exercise so they don't get injured”¹⁰⁷. When talking about martial arts, getting injured could be a concern, as one may expect that in a fighting sport injuries are very frequent²¹⁴. What is not clear to the general public is that traditional martial arts, the ones we refer to in this paper, are not necessarily violent or aimed at fighting *per se*²¹⁵. In fact, in Shotokan Karate for example there are three main training areas: kihon, or fundamentals training, teaches the individual movements, techniques, and combinations of Shotokan training; kata, or forms, are the heart of Karate. Shotokan has traditionally had 26 kata that are used to transmit the art. They contain active combinations of almost every technique used and can be extensively interpreted into different fighting methodologies through the study of Bunkai or the application of Kata; Kumite, or sparring, is the actual application of these techniques and combinations to another human being²¹⁵. Kumite is only 1/3 of the Karate sport and because of the gradual way

Shotokan Karate Kumite is introduced to students, according to their experience, Karate is one of the safest martial arts, with taekwondo and Tai Chi and it is no more dangerous than national collegiate athletic association (NCAA) sports²¹⁵. It is a misnomer therefore that traditional martial arts are inappropriate for older adults.

Few studies investigated the reason why people, and specifically senior athletes, practise martial arts²¹⁶. As in all other sports, the motivation of martial arts practitioners varies across types of martial arts disciplines, competition orientation and past experiences²¹⁶. In a recent study by Fuller and Llyod, 500 martial artists of different ages, testified about the positive effect of the martial arts on their well-being perception²¹⁷. This should help thinking about the possible benefits that martial arts exert on the older practitioners' health perception, well-being, and behaviours.

Considering the interest of elderly people in the practice of martial arts, it was pragmatic to investigate what motivated older adults to the practice. As there was scant literature, we decided to ask older people what encouraged them to join and what made them continue. We utilised a qualitative approach in a pilot study to build and maintain a close relationship with participants and thus improve the open and frank exchange of information²¹⁸.

Methods

To follow Crouch and Mckenzie's guidelines on qualitative studies and to facilitate the open and frank exchange of information, authors decided to select no more than four participants. Several research questions were considered, as temporality and enjoyment, following the Csikszentmihalyi's (1990) flow theory concepts²¹⁹.

After approval of the ethics committee, the authors recruited four participants that had been practising martial arts for more than 2 years and were over 60 years of age. All subjects were informed verbally and in writing that they could withdraw anytime and that their participation was voluntary. Participants received a description of the research and a consent form, to be signed before beginning the study. Three recruited subjects were from the USA and one from the Netherlands. Participants were assigned with the following pseudonyms according to their gender: Julie, Erica, Bob, and Jan. This is a mixed-gender study, with two females and two males. The two women were 62 and 71 years old and the two males were 70 and 74 years old.

Selected subjects were required to be able to understand questions and to be actively involved in martial arts.

Interviews were conducted by phone. Participant recruitment was conducted using the “snow-ball” effect through a participant that was involved in the seniors’ national team of Poomse. Interviews were recorded and then transcribed. After transcription, they were re-sent to the interviewed subject to confirm the content. The researcher completed data analysis with guidance from Braun and Clarke²²⁰. In this concept the researcher transcribes and re-reads the recordings, aiming to understand the content. Once familiar with the data, the researcher identifies preliminary codes and analyses the code by combining or splitting them according to overarching themes. This is followed by a deeper review to question whether to combine, refine, separate, or discard initial themes. Data within themes should cohere meaningfully, while there should be clear and identifiable distinctions between themes. Subsequently, the researcher provides theme names and clear working definitions which capture the essence of each theme in a concise unified story. Data analysis comes in writing using extract examples that relate to the themes, research question, and literature, supported with empirical evidence that addresses the research question.

Transcripts of interviews and observation notes were organised according to participant pseudonyms. Following the structure of Janssen and Stube, open coding began with reflexive journaling initially during the analysis process²²¹. After every interview, the author recorded an audit trail with detailed notes and observations. The researcher considered the original field notes during the next step for later review and understanding of the transcripts. The study included only single interviews and there was no saturation because of time and cost limitations. To ensure the data trustworthiness, the researcher checked that the transcript of the answers matched exactly what the participants meant, by reading to the participants the answer he noted and asking them if the notes were accurate. The study was approved by the ethics committee of the University of the West of Scotland.

Ethics approval is available in Appendix A

Interview questions are available in Appendix B.

Table 4 Interviews' themes

Macro theme	Sub-theme
Socio-cultural influence	Media influence Ageism Networking/social activity Social inclusion Family support Cultural/family background Active behaviour
Spiritualism	Spiritual beliefs Spiritualism
Psychological well being	Active behaviours Mental health Coping skills Self-development Self-esteem Social inclusion
External factors	Location Ageism Family support

Results

The interview subjects were active people that trained almost every day and exhibited confidence and acceptance of their body image. The four subjects all highlighted the psychological benefits of practising martial arts. They highlight the feeling of belonging to a community with shared interests, confronting each other and planning trips for competitions. A strong sense of belonging was revealed and, at the same time, an important sense of stability for their identity. They also underlined the relationship with younger athletes, as a stimulating positive comparison that motivated participants in intra or extra-personal processes to improve themselves. It became clear the subjects referred to the dojo and the martial arts not only as a place or a sport but a micro-community, where older adults felt active and socially engaged. Coding the interviews, the authors found four macro themes. The thematic analysis results show 4 macro themes: 1) Socio-cultural influence 2) Spiritualism 3) Psychological well being 4) External factors.

The theme of sociocultural influence was identified after coding all those cultural and social beliefs that might have promoted the practice of martial arts among the study participants when they decide to join and coding all social influences that affect participants' choice of training and lifestyle. This main theme included other sub-themes such as media influence, ageism, networking/social activity, social inclusion, family support, cultural/family background, and active behaviour. The Socio-cultural macro theme and its subthemes can be found in the following sentences of the interview, as when Julie tells us:

“I was inspired by a kung-fu series, popular in the sixties”.

Others instead showed that the cultural and family background was the main reason to approach these sports, as bob mentioned:

“My father was a boxer and wanted me to box”.

While Erica shared the possibility to connect with people and new communities through martial arts:

“I started to learn and practice (specifically taekwondo) as a means of relating more closely to the Korean environment and gaining a better understanding of the culture and its people.”

Julie mentioned being judged because of her age and being a victim of ageism:

“Social prejudices describe older adults as weak! Training helps to understand that we can improve, that, for example, we can break a board. This is very important to gain confidence in yourself”.

According to Julie, being involved in martial arts seemed to fight loneliness:

Julie: *“Martial arts help me a lot to find a good balance in my social activities. “To meet a lot of people and make very good connections”*

Helping to create possible networking or friendships. This finds support in Erica’s statement: *“It (Taekwon-Do) has played a central part in my social life”.*

At the same time, participants made it very clear that to keep practising martial arts and being deeply involved requires some family support. For example, Erica said:

“Without my family and friends’ support, I would not be able and encouraged to continue in TKD”.

Jan underlined the positive effect of martial arts on social group activities: *“Very often we have a beer after training”*

The interviews also showed us that participants were generally active people. Bob said:

“I am an active person, and I would be active also if I didn’t practice martial arts”

And Julie:

“I travel a lot because of my athletic career”.

Jan confirmed:

“Usually I take care of the house and my daughter. I go buy food, I clean the house and I read a lot. I am very interested in comparative philosophy of religion.”

It is very clear that seniors involved in martial arts have quite active lifestyles. If this depends on the martial arts or their natural behaviour is not understandable from these interviews but would be definitely worth to research in future studies.

Spiritualism

The second macro theme is Spiritualism, which includes Spiritual beliefs too. Previous researchers identified a link between active behaviours and spiritualism in later life⁹⁸. This seems to be confirmed by our participants too. For example, bob said: *“about 40 years ago, I decided to be a Buddhist”*,

Jan:

“I am very interested in comparative philosophy of religion”

And Julie:

“Every morning I wake up, I pray and meditate”.

This does not necessarily mean that believers are active people, but let us understand that the spiritual component in a physical activity might be an important reason to involve older adults. In fact, erica says:

“In TKD there is a philosophy and an underlying belief system (ex. The 5 tenets of taekwondo) that distinguish it from many other martial arts and fighting sports”.

This link between spiritualism and later life could be well explained considering Maslow’s theory of needs, where the latest steps of the pyramids, usually achievable in our late adulthood, are associated with the research of transcendent needs⁹⁸. Therefore, it would be necessary to consider spiritualism in the promotion and planning of future physical activity programs in later life.

Psychological well being

The third macro theme is Psychological well being. This theme spreads in other subthemes that are 1)Active behaviours 2)Mental health 3)Coping skills 4)Self-development 5)Self-esteem 6)Social inclusion. In the interview we can find this topic for example in the following sentences:

Julie: *“when I was young I suffered from depression and anorexia, probably, because of I and my family moved very often. Martial arts have been very relevant in my healing process.”*

Bob: *“martial arts really help a lot for mental and physical growth!”*

In other sentences, the relation to psychological well-being was more implicit. For example, Julie says:

Martial art is a way to connect with the world and with people”.

And Erika:

“It (taekwondo) has played a central part in my social life”,

While Jan:

“Most of the people come to train not only for the fitness or the martial art but for the social context that they can find in the dojo”.

These sentences make us think the participants are quite well socially included and have a good social life, thanks to the martial art. Participants seemed to have an active behaviour and practising other physical activities as Jan said:

“I also do jogging and fitness training”.

Other sentences by the subjects let us understand how the martial art has helped them to improve their coping skills, self-esteem, and self-development. In fact, Julie said:

“At the beginning, I was afraid of sparring, but then, training, I learned to cope with this fear” and “this (taekwondo training) helps to gain confidence in themselves and to say: I can do that, also if I am old, I can still do it!”

Bringing much attention to themes of coping and self-esteem. Erika instead lets us understand how important this sport was for her self-development:

“The quality of my life, world outlook, understanding of myself, others and interaction with society has been heavily influenced through my TKD training and practice.”

As Jan:

“Martial arts really help a lot for mental and physical growth!”

These might not be new findings, as some other researchers previously linked the practice of martial arts to psychological well-being¹²⁹, but they bring more support to a scant literature base and above all, it focuses the attention on older practitioners, underlying new research paths to investigate.

External factors

The last macro theme the authors outlined is External factors. During interviews, authors noted some factors other than intrinsic that might have influenced participants' choice or practice of the martial art. These factors have been listed as “external” and they mainly include location, ageism (or social prejudices) and family support.

Previous studies suggested that barriers for physical activity in later life were discomfort or unsafe locations, ageism, and lack of social and family support²²²⁻²²⁴. We can confirm these findings from the quotes of our participants. In fact, Julie said:

“I am very lucky because my dojo and gym are next to my home” and “most people, training, get surprised by themselves when they perform a certain technique that they thought impossible! This helps them to gain confidence in themselves and to say: “I can do that, also if I am old, I can still do it!”

While Erika made very clear how important is to be supported by family and friends to keep having an active lifestyle:

“Without my family and friends' support, I would not be able and encouraged to continue in TKD”.

These findings showed us that it is important to act on a social inclusion and prejudice-avoidance policy to make programs of physical activity more suitable and attractive in later life.

Discussion

This study resulted in observed themes concerning active ageing, the practice of martial arts and socio-cultural influence, spiritualism, psychological well-being, and other external factors. Results showed older adults practising martial arts had a generally active and independent lifestyle with different hobbies and a satisfying social inclusion. Older athletes seem not to focus on their chronological age but more on their physical and mental abilities. Interestingly, particular characteristics of discipline and “structure” of martial arts (cit. Bob), and the community built around the dojo “as a family” (cit. Erica) were cited to improve older adults’ perception of general well-being.

The results seem to be in line with previous studies performed on different populations such as the Fuller and Lloyd study that underlined the practice of martial arts improved well-being perception and social inclusion among participants²¹⁷. Other previous studies suggested Karate training was able to improve the social-emotional and executive functioning of children (8-11 years) with autism spectrum disorder (ASD)²²⁵. Another study on taekwondo, based on 31 subjects (18.83±3.49 years of age) showed this martial art training increased levels of self-esteem and personal competence, leading to a better social life²²⁶. Additionally, in 403 Chinese adolescents (13.66 ±1.14 years of age, mean duration of practice 1.36 ±1.33 years), the practice of martial arts was positively correlated with general self-efficacy, positive affect, and active coping strategy²²⁷. Associations between self-esteem and martial arts practice have been observed in the literature previously, where for example, self-esteem was directly correlated to experience and winnings in martial arts²²⁸. Similar results were found in other studies focused on general physical activity, and not martial arts, as a tool to improve health and well-being in older adults. Bae et al showed that light physical activities were positively associated with physical health and life satisfaction in senior participants²²⁹. Similarly to martial arts, physical activity has strong effects on self-

efficacy and improvements in well-being²³⁰. At the same time, practising physical activity, such as martial arts, can contribute to social inclusion in later life²³¹.

The benefits of martial arts are similar to those observed with general physical activity as a tool for health and well-being improvement in seniors. In this context, the authors suggest martial arts should be considered appropriate for older adults and could be considered a viable public health initiative. This pilot study confirmed the results of previous research, strengthening the link between practising martial arts and general well-being. At the same time, it brings new evidence and directions for future studies. For example, while previous studies on martial arts and psychological well-being were mainly focused on young or middle-aged participants¹²⁹, this study focuses on older adults. This study highlighted the spiritual component of martial art that could address spiritual needs in later life, proposing martial arts as a possible intervention for older adults to be physically and socially active, as a lack of motivation has been proposed in this demographic²⁰⁷. The research finds positive results in training older adults with young people, motivating participants an intra or extra-personal processes to improve themselves, but it brings new questions, which future research may wish to address. For example, we did not consider how the inclusion of older adults would affect class planning from the instructors' point of view. Secondly, older adults are physiologically disparate from younger adults, and how training has been or should be adapted for older adults remains to be elucidated.

This study was not without limitations which we must accept. For example, the small sample size means that these data cannot be extrapolated to the entire older adult martial arts community. However, this was a pilot study and therefore this approach was appropriate, and utilised information and experienced generated herein to conduct a larger confirmatory study. Secondly, the addition of age-matched non-martial art but physically active group, and an age-matched sedentary group would permit direct

comparisons between martial arts participants and physically active participants, and sedentary participants. This would elucidate the effects of martial arts above and beyond traditional physical activity in terms of well-being in older adults.

Conclusions

In conclusion, it appears practising martial arts can improve general well-being and physical and social active behaviours in older adults. Four subjects all highlighted benefits on general well-being which were attributed to practising martial arts. They also communicated external factors such as family support were necessary for maintaining their interest and how they were projected to the world of spirituality. A strong sense of belonging was revealed and concomitantly, an important sense of stability in their identity was evident. Therefore, it should be considered the dojo is not only a place where practising traditional martial arts is undertaken but is manifest as a micro-community, where older adults feel active, and socially engaged. Authors believe this pilot study contributes novel findings to current research as most papers referring to older adults and martial arts are focused on Tai Chi, leaving other traditional martial arts (e.g., Karate, taekwondo, judo, etc.) underexamined.

Chapter IV: Age, Karate Participation and Self-esteem and Coping

Introduction

Coping refers to the conscious effort to solve personal and interpersonal problems to try to master, minimise or tolerate stress and conflict²³². Coping is strongly related to self-esteem that is an essential component of mental health and well-being being^{233,234}. Self-esteem can be defined as ‘the overall affective evaluation of one’s worth, value or importance’⁵⁰. Recent evidence indicates that superior coping skills and high levels of self-esteem are associated with a better quality of life in older individuals^{235,236}, making this topic important for public health.

According to Weiten et al., It is possible to recognise four main coping strategies as appraisal-focused (adaptive cognitive) strategies, directed towards challenging personal assumptions, or problem-focused (adaptive behavioural) ones, aimed at reducing or eliminating stressors, or emotion-focused and occupation-focused strategies; the former are applied to changes in personal emotional reactions, while the latter involve lasting occupation(s), which generates positive feedback²³⁷. The success of coping strategies might be affected by external factors such as religion, nutrition, exercise, sleep, physical fitness, and relaxation techniques such as progressive muscle relaxation²³⁸. Regardless, coping strategies, like self-esteem, are dynamic and temporal and change with age^{239,240}.

Although coping and self-esteem have been widely explored from within sports psychology generally, research specifically concerning combat sports competitors is relatively scarce^{241–243}. This is surprising given the relatively widespread belief that martial arts are good for the improvement of self-esteem, coping, well-being, and confidence^{244,245}. For example, a comparison of Karate Kyokushin athletes and track and field athletes reported that martial arts athletes exhibited a significantly higher level of self-

confidence and used more effective strategies for coping²⁴⁶. Moreover, advanced Karate athletes have also been reported to have a superior level of self-esteem²²⁸. Taken together, these studies support the concept that Karate training can improve levels of self-esteem²⁴⁷.

There is less literature examining the effects of martial arts on self-esteem or coping strategies in older competitors. Some studies have reported improvements in ‘movement-based approaches. For example, Tai Chi programs have been reported to improve self-esteem and coping skills in older adults^{248–250}. However, this is not a consistent finding, even within the same school of training. Trulson et al. Found that traditional taekwondo was effective at improving self-esteem, while modern taekwondo was not²⁵¹, with other studies supporting this finding²⁵². Truslon et al. Suggest that this is to attribute to the intrinsic philosophy and structure of the martial art. In fact, traditional taekwondo training is more focused on respect for others, humility, confidence, responsibility, honesty, perseverance and honour when compared to the modern martial art and traditional taekwondo athletes take an oath to use taekwondo only for self-defence or to defend the weak. Athletes of modern taekwondo do not take such oath. Therefore, it appears there is some ambiguity concerning older martial art competitors and self-esteem. Furthermore, few studies have assessed both self-esteem and coping simultaneously. Even fewer have considered how coping and self-esteem change with age in Karate competitors, as shown in the results of the scoping review where most studies were focused on non-competitive amateurs.

One pertinent limitation of the previous literature is that when relating to self-esteem, much research has been qualitative and asked martial arts athletes if their practice improved their coping or self-esteem. This is likely to lead to a classic type I error in the form of the *cum hoc ergo propter hoc* fallacy, whereby martial arts athletes attribute their self-esteem and coping to martial arts practice, despite the questionable-cause logical fallacy. As this association has rarely been objectively measured using

validated scales, the interplay between age, years of martial arts practice, and coping and self-esteem warranted further examination quantitatively. Specifically, we thought it pertinent to examine whether self-esteem and coping were associated with years of martial arts practice, independent of age. Considering the recent interest in coping and self-esteem as possible predictors of quality of life, and considering coping and self-esteem evolves during the lifespan, there is a paucity of data concerning coping and self-esteem in relation to age among martial art competitors. Therefore, the aim of this pilot study was to investigate both coping and self-esteem in a mixed-age group of Karate athletes to assess if there were any age effects.

Methods

Recruitment

The authors recruited part of the participants online, part in person, during Karate events, and part thanks to Karate associations.

Participants were recruited online with to the use of social media platforms. The author used the “Forms. Office” software to rewrite the questionnaires in an online format in English and Italian. Once the questionnaires were ready, the software generated a link, that the author posted on different Karate groups in social media and to other people known to be practicing martial arts, asking to contribute to a snowball effect. The author considered the virtual feedback to the social media post, as “likes” as an indication to understand the number of people that saw the link with the questionnaire.

Other athletes were recruited during a Scottish Karate competition, after approval of the local Scottish Karate governing body, part of W.K.F. Before the official event, competitors with more than one year of experience and practising only Shotokan style were asked to volunteer for the study. Italian Karate

competitors were contacted with a snowball effect, starting from a contact with the Italian Karate federation *fijklam*, W.K.F. approved. The authors contacted Italian participants by email on the suggestion of the Italian Karate instructors.

Data collection

Volunteers were provided with an envelope containing the coping orientation to problems experienced (cope) inventory and the Rosenberg questionnaire. The cope is a validated instrument, designed to measure effective and ineffective ways to cope with a stressful life event²⁵³ and therefore assesses responses that are considered functional and dysfunctional²⁵⁴. The COPE Inventory is a tool designed to evaluate various coping responses, encompassing both functional and dysfunctional aspects. It incorporates theoretical foundations to assess a wide range of coping strategies. Additionally, the inventory includes at least two pairs of polar-opposite tendencies, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of an individual's coping mechanisms²⁵⁴. The Rosenberg self-esteem scale is a 10-item scale that measures global self-worth by measuring both positive and negative feelings about the self. The scale is believed to be unidimensional. All items are answered using a 4-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree⁵⁴. It is the most utilised measure of global self-esteem for any age-group^{255,256}. It has been used in well-being research on all age groups, and it is considered to be an appropriate measure of self-esteem in the elderly²⁵⁶.

As not to influence responses, athletes were not informed of the goal of the study and were asked to complete the questionnaire after the competition and to return it to their instructor at the gym, where a research member collected completed questionnaires. The same questionnaires, in the validated Italian versions, were scanned and delivered to Italian participants by email. Once returned, anonymous

questionnaires were kept in a secure database at u.w.s. Lanarkshire campus is accessible only to the authors.

Data analysis

Relationships between variables were determined using Pearson’s product-moment correlation coefficient. Alpha level was not set dichotomously as 'significant' or otherwise as recommended by the American statistical association ²⁵⁷ (Hulbert et al., 2019). The effect size for correlations was interpreted using thresholds of 0.2, 0.5, and 0.8 for small, moderate, and large effects (Cohen, 1988). Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD).

Results

The study included 67 participants (range 15 – 71yrs), 24 females and 32 males. Participants years of training range is 5 – 59 yrs. The author has estimated to reach in total 150 potential participants, according the online feedbacks on the social media platform, but only 56 questionnaires were completed and returned, showing a failure rate of around 63%.

Table 5 Participant characteristics

Participant	Nationality n (%)	Gender n (%)	Age	Years of training
	UK = 26 (38.5) BR = 1 (1.5) IT = 40 (60)	Female 25 (37.3) Male 40- (62.7)	34.6 ± 20.01	16 ± 11

Table 6 Mean scores for Scope and scope items

Item (arbitrary units)	Mean	Std. Deviation
Positive reinterpretation and growth	12.6	2.64
Mental disengagement	8.66	2.82
Focus on and venting of emotions	9.03	2.76
Use of instrumental social support	10.9	3.07
Active coping	11.9	2.81
Denial	6.52	2.21
Religious coping	7.65	4.61
Humour	10.0	3.45
Behavioural disengagement	6.12	2.53
Restraint	10.0	2.38
Use of emotional support	9.85	3.26
Substance use	4.33	1.26
Acceptance	9.92	2.85
Suppression of competing activities	10.0	2.71
Planning	12.5	2.86
Problem focus	57.5	8.4
Emotion focus	47	9.1
Avoidant coping response	22.5	5.3

Table 7 Mean Scores for Rosenberg and Sub items

Item (arbitrary units)	Mean	Standard deviation
On the whole, I am satisfied with myself	3.4	0.6
At times I think I am not good at all	2.4	1.1
I think that I have a number of good qualities	3.5	0.6
I am able to do things as well as most other people	3.2	0.8
I feel I do not have much to be proud of	2.7	1.1
I certainly feel useless at times	3.3	0.9
I feel that I am a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others	2.3	1.2
I wish I could have more respect for myself	2.9	1.1
All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure	3.5	0.8

I take a positive attitude toward myself	2.3	1.1
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For the cope inventory, there were significant correlations between increasing age and mental disengagement, active coping, and planning (table 6). Overall, after combining scores for all 10 items (including reverse scoring for items 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9) there was no association between the age of Karate competitors and total self-esteem. However, there were correlations for individual items.

Table 8 Correlation values

Item (arbitrary units)		Age	Years of training
Positive reinterpretation and growth	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.357	0.326
	P	0.086	0.12
Mental disengagement	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.533**	-0.2
	P	0.007	0.349
Focus on and venting of emotions	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.387	-0.373
	P	0.062	0.073
Use of instrumental social support	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.019	0.071
	P	0.928	0.743
Active coping	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.443*	0.387
	P	0.03	0.062
Denial	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.128	-0.128
	P	0.552	0.551
Religious coping	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.333	-0.276
	P	0.112	0.191
Humour	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.203	0.069
	P	0.341	0.748
Behavioural disengagement	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.2	-0.245
	P	0.35	0.249
Restraint	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.325	-0.044

	P	0.121	0.837
Use of emotional support	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.277	-0.16
	P	0.19	0.456
Substance use	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.075	0.265
	P	0.728	0.211
Acceptance	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.285	-0.335
	P	0.176	0.109
Suppression of competing activities	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.147	0.093
	P	0.494	0.665
Planning	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.615**	0.543**
	P	0.001	0.006
Problem focus	Pearson's correlation coefficient	.424*	0.313
	P	0.039	0.137
Emotion focus	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.286	-0.243
	P	0.175	0.253
Coping response	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.548**	-0.414*
	P	0.006	0.044

For the Rosenberg questionnaire, there was no significant association between age and the total score (table 9). However, there were significant correlations between age and items 6, 7, 8, and 10.

Table 9 Correlation coefficients between age, training years, and Rosenberg items

Item (arbitrary units)		Age	Years of training
Total	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.651**	-0.292
	P	0.001	0.166
Rq1	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.170	-0.067
	P	0.186	0.605
Rq2	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.057	0.051
	P	0.663	0.699
Rq3	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.210	-0.126
	P	0.102	0.330
Rq4	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.153	-0.006
	P	0.236	0.962
Rq5	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.144	0.106
	P	0.263	0.411
Rq6	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.210	0.114
	P	0.107	0.385

Rq7	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.032	-0.040
	P	0.081	0.749
Rq8	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.133	0.133
	P	0.289	0.290
Rq9	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.033	0.050
	P	0.792	0.695
Rq10	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.055	0.037
	P	0.661	0.770

**correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed); *correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Discussion

This pilot study aimed to evaluate coping skills and self-esteem in Karate competitors, to understand if the age of years of Shotokan Karate practice is associated with coping strategies or self-esteem. The main findings of the present study were (1) age was associated with mental disengagement, greater active coping, and probl-focused, which was not related to years of Karate training; (2) greater use of planning and use of avoidant approaches were associated with increasing age and years of training; (3) increasing age and years of training were associated with greater scores on items related to self-criticism

Results suggest that independently of age, self-esteem seems to be affected by years of training. This is in line with previous literature concerning self-esteem. Nemcek et al. Showed individuals with higher levels of athletic competence experienced greater self-esteem²⁵⁸, and specifically, elite athletes had greater self-esteem than non-elite athletes and non-athletes^{258,259}. In the study by Nemcek et al., the Rosenberg total score of self-esteem was 31 (average) for elite athletes. In this study, the total score was quite close. The difference in results might be related to the fact that Nemecek et al. Involved 716 participants aged up to 30 years, while our study involved 56 people with a different average age.

Scientific research indicates that self-esteem is generally affected by physical activity⁸⁷. There is evidence that self-esteem can be improved, even in later life, via physical activity because of the improvements relative to an attractive body, strength, and physical condition²⁶⁰. A randomised controlled trial by Mcauley et al. Examined the growth of multidimensional self-esteem over a 12-month period (6-month exercise intervention and 6-month follow-up) in 174 sedentary older adults (65.5 years old). In that study participants engaged in either walking or stretching/toning program²⁶⁰. Mcauley et al. Used the Rosenberg self-esteem scale to evaluate participants' self-esteem and found correlations between

self-esteem and activity and changes in physical fitness, body fat, and self-efficacy. Both walking and toning groups had an increase in global esteem. Walkers passed from 39.62 to 39.89, while the toning group passed from 40.90 to 41.29. These results, especially the ones reported by the walking group are different from our results, probably because Mcauley et al considered a 6-month intervention and our participants were much younger than Mcauley et al participants' average age was 65.5. Therefore, the authors suggested being physically active can increase self-esteem. Taken together, it appears that physical activity can increase self-esteem, and being more proficient in exercise performance (e.g. Being an elite athlete) can augment this effect.

Previous researchers have suggested martial arts are a useful tool to improve participants' well-being. Fuller and Lloyd 2020 confirm that adult martial arts practitioners' self-report of their perceived engagement with martial arts was useful to cope with stress and improve well-being²¹⁷. This data included 500 participants across all ages and ranges and data using qualitative methodology. The sample of the study is based mostly on Tai Chi practitioners (51%) and Karate athletes (43%), followed by Qi Gong (21%), Kung Fu (6%), Aikido (4.5%), and Jujitsu (3%). Therefore, this does not really help to have an overview of martial arts, but mostly on two of them, and mostly East Asian traditional martial arts. Furthermore, fuller and Lloyd used a qualitative methodology allowing participants to express themselves and to comment on their own perception of reality. Thus, this likely led to *cum hoc ergo propter hoc* fallacy, whereby martial arts athletes attributed effects on well-being to martial arts practice, despite the questionable-cause logical fallacy.

Effects reported herein concerning martial arts effects on self-esteem are in line with previous research on general physical activity. In fact, literature reviews have noted ~60% of studies report a positive association between physical activity participation and self-esteem²⁶¹. Unfortunately, not all physical

activities have the same effects on self-esteem as for example weight training was found to be more effective than aerobic exercise²⁶¹. Among menopausal women, walking and yoga interventions failed to enhance global or physical self-esteem but improved subdomain esteem relative to physical condition and strength (for walking) and body attractiveness (for both walking and yoga)²⁶². This highlights the need to investigate, as in this study, the specific correlation between martial arts, coping and self-esteem to evaluate the specific efficacy of these traditional arts.

In terms of martial arts and self-esteem and coping, only three studies have used the Rosenberg or the cope questionnaires^{243,248,249}. No other previous papers gave a deep description of the martial art training protocol as performed exercises or techniques and the order of performance. Moreover, only a few researchers have described the style performed by practitioners^{246,251}. This can create problems with the generalizability of findings, as stated by Smith et al. “studies examining martial arts have significant methodological problems that limit the generalizability of findings, such as conceptual and definitional issue²⁶³”. The aforementioned studies also focused on specific age groups, leaving open the question if the outcomes had to be related to the martial art *per se* or to the age of the participants. Most studies have evaluated coping or self-esteem independently, leaving unexplored the possibility that coping and self-esteem can affect each other.

This research instead has been very specific on the choice of a precise martial art and even its own style and rules. The authors have focused on different age groups trying to investigate the possible influence of age on coping and self-esteem, besides the influence of the martial art *per se*. Furthermore, differently from most previous studies, the authors have tried to answer the question if coping and self-esteem can really affect each other.

Limitations

This paper has some limitations, which we must accept. Firstly, the research only included Shotokan Karate. However, this is a problem with the literature generally, that a variety of styles and teaching approaches exist. Our decision to incorporate Shotokan Karate was based upon the fact that modern Karate Shotokan is wkf approved. Moreover, Shotokan is the most practised style in the UK and maybe in the world^{264,265} and the WKF is the only Karate governing body approved by the Olympic committee. By focusing on modern WKF approved Shotokan, we have attempted to assess the effects of a well-defined style, and one that is the most widely practised. A second limitation is the small number of participants and so larger confirmatory studies are required to extend these results.

Conclusions

Modern Shotokan Karate athletes rarely adopt mental disengagement as a coping method when ageing, in favour of a more active coping strategy based on planning. Self-esteem was not correlated to age, but there was a positive correlation between age and other subcategories of self-esteem as feeling more useful and satisfied with their self-respect. Unfortunately, increasing age was associated with a lower value for individual worthiness and a positive approach toward self. The study has also provided evidence that increased self-esteem is associated with increased positive reinterpretation, increased instrumental social support, increased active coping, great use of humour, increased acceptance and with reduced behavioural disengagement. On the basis of this evidence, we suggest that the practice of Shotokan Karate should be taken into consideration in public health initiatives to improve self-esteem and coping strategies in adults.

Chapter V: Feasibility of an online Karate intervention for elderly people

Introduction

The number of older adults is growing in most countries of the world²⁶⁶. In England, for example, it is expected an increase of 50% in the number of 80-90-years-old between 1995 and 2050²⁶⁶. The ageing population presents many opportunities and also several public health challenges that we need to prepare for as people are living longer, but not healthier⁴. Increasing age is associated with increased physical inactivity leading to chronic diseases such as atherosclerosis, with follow-up effects like coronary heart disease, myocardial insufficiency, hypertension, stroke, type ii diabetes, obesity, several types of cancer, osteoporosis and sarcopenia²⁶⁶. This has important financial consequences too. For example, in Canada, the annual economic burden of physical inactivity is \$5.3 billion, while in Australia is 7%, in Switzerland 1.8% of total direct costs, in the United Kingdom 1.5% of total direct costs and in the United States 2.4% of total direct costs²⁶⁷.

Ageing issues are not related only to physiological changes, but also to social inclusion and social prejudices. Older people are especially exposed to loneliness and social isolation with more than 2 million people in England over the age of 75 living alone²³. This can be dangerous as social isolation in older people is related to reduced everyday physical activity and greater sedentary time²⁶⁸. New data show that isolation and loneliness increase risk of dementia by a third and 20% of cases of depression^{269,270}. Furthermore, over the years, prejudices have spread about the elderly, leading to ageism. Ageism, according to Larsen and Solem, is as “negative or positive stereotypes, prejudice and/or discrimination against (or to the advantage of) elderly people on the basis of their chronological age or on the basis of a perception of them as being ‘old’ or ‘elderly’^{16,17}. The consequence of ageism and social

isolation becomes a matter of physical health as these phenomena are linked with increased mortality, increased incidence of heart disease and functional decline²²

The importance of being physically active

Being physically active is probably the best way to treat and prevent age-related conditions, helping to save costs on public health^{266,267}. Physical activity has been associated with reduced risk of several chronic conditions such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, cancer, hypertension, obesity, depression, osteoporosis, balance problems, and difficulty walking^{56,271}.

According to the WHO, all adults aged over 18 should do at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity physical activity throughout the week, or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity physical activity throughout the week, or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity.¹¹⁵ those with poor mobility should perform physical activity to enhance balance and prevent falls, three or more days per week. Muscle-strengthening activities should be completed involving major muscle groups, two or more days a week.¹¹⁵

Physical activity, above all when in small groups, is one of the best ways to promote social inclusion building relationships between participants based on shared interests and similar needs, and working via compensation for lost meaningful social connections²⁷². Unfortunately, because of barriers such as stereotypes, ageism, geographical location, access to affordable community-based exercise programs, qualified exercise trainers and a general aversion to the gym environment, most older adults do not take part in physical activity^{16,17,273}.

COVID-19

The level of physical inactivity in older adults has recently increased with the social distancing guidelines part of governmental responses to Covid-19²⁷⁴. The pandemic had an unequal impact as people in later life had a greater risk of the effects of coronavirus. People aged 80 and above were 70 times more likely to die than those under 40²⁷⁵. The restrictions have also exposed isolated people to more unhealthy behaviours as since lockdown began, a third have been smoking more (36%) and around three in ten (32%) have been drinking more²⁷⁵. Mental health was also affected by restrictions and individuals who live alone, are more likely to have said that their mental health had suffered during lockdown (43% versus 36% overall)²⁷⁵. This is an important aspect to consider as loneliness increase the risk of dementia and depression in older subjects^{269,270}. On the other hand, in order to connect people, several remote technologies and apps have been developed and the use of digital platforms such as teleconferencing or videoconferencing could be used effectively to deliver services such as fitness classes or social activities while maintaining social distancing²⁷⁶. Given the issues of social distancing and Covid-19, there is a need to investigate remote methods of supporting older adults to maintain or increase their physical activity.

Why Karate?

Among different physical activities, evidence demonstrates many older adults enjoy practising martial arts^{94,95}. The reason for popularity among older adults is not clear but martial arts have a very strong link with religion, spiritualism, and empathy⁹⁶. This may play a role in the popularity as they have been considered motivational support for physical activity in the elderly^{98 54,55}. One of the most popular martial arts in the world is Karate, with the number of participants estimated to be in excess of 50 million worldwide¹³⁶. Karate seems to bring many health benefits across different age groups, including those in later life, such as improving bone mineral density (BMD), strength and balance^{141 129,138}.

Unfortunately, besides the beneficial effects, Karate has not received the same attention as other martial arts such as Tai Chi, which is one of the most popular activities recommended for older adults by many national health authorities such as the NHS¹⁰⁵.

Given that as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, older people engaged in more unhealthy habits became more isolated, more physically inactive, and were affected by physical and mental distress^{277,278,279}. When Covid-19 pandemic started, group activities could not be performed and people were asked to keep social and physical distancing or isolation^{280,281}. This has definitely affected the practice of Karate and martial arts as these sports are usually performed in schools, involving more than one participant²⁸². Consequently, this might have promoted a sedentary behaviour among martial artists and people in general²⁸¹.

To cope with this situation, remote group exercise sessions have been trialled for other exercise types, as they were previously found to be helpful in improving some aspects of general health as glycaemic control or in treating knee osteoarthritis^{283,284}.

Home-based group exercise has some benefits as online training modality are usually cost and time-effective^{285,286}.

However, remote group exercise has rarely been trialled with martial arts in older adults. The requirement to engage with technology, and delivering kata and Kumite over the internet to this group may be difficult and the feasibility of delivery is unknown.

Therefore, the aim of the study was to develop this feasibility study to evaluate the retention, adherence, adverse events, usability, and enjoyment of an online Karate class.

Methods

Study design

The adapted Karate class for older adults was a single-group feasibility study, aimed at adults aged 60 years and over, with a minimum 1-year experience in martial arts. Participants were invited to follow one online adapted Karate class, delivered by a certified Karate instructor using web technology. At the end of the Karate, class subjects were asked to complete the social and community opportunities profile (scope) short form validated questionnaire and a feasibility and acceptability survey created especially for the study. The experiment was approved by the University of The West of Scotland ethics committee.

Participants and recruitment

Six men and nine women aged 60 years and over were recruited through different channels using snowball sampling. Participants had an average age of 72 years. Recruitment was undertaken by engaging with a variety of channels to access older adults. These included working with older adult advocacy groups (Scottish association for older adults), social media, and regional Karate schools that were not delivering classes due to the Covid-19 restrictions. To be included in the study, participants had to have access to, and be able to use remote technology and have sufficient functional capacity to perform physical activity. Participants were excluded based on the following self-reported criteria: inability to stand unaided, acute or terminal illness likely to compromise exercise participation, unstable or ongoing cardiovascular/respiratory disorder, musculoskeletal or neurological disease or functional limitations disrupting voluntary movement or that might have limited training, unable to read and understand a questionnaire, or inability to commit to the study and its requirements, technology included.

For the classes, online ‘meetings’ were organised by the association itself. Participants were divided into three classes/meetings. The association’s leader scheduled classes and sent invitation links by email for the zoom platform. At the given time and date, participants clicked on the link and joined the class

Intervention

Participants were given instructions by email on the date and time for the intervention and a link to connect on the chosen platform. To deliver a good quality and safe service and to focus on all participants, classes were limited to a number of maximum five volunteers. Each class followed a similar format covering stretching and flexibility, Karate technique, focus, and muscle strengthening exercise, but was adapted to each participant according to their needs and ability. Class lasted around 1 hour of physical exercise and extra 15-20 minutes for the social activity.

Stretching and flexibility

The class started with adapted stretching for upper and lower limbs, trying to keep volunteers close to hold a chair or wall in case of balance issues. Stretching exercises included:

Seated knee to chest: sits in your chair, and while seated, grasp your right knee and slowly pull it towards your chest. Hold this position for 10 to 30 seconds.. Do the same with the other leg.

Soleus stretch: stand up facing a wall. Step your right foot in front of your left and place both hands on the wall in front of you for support. Once you feel comfortable, begin to slowly bend your knees until you begin to feel a stretch in your lower leg. Hold this position for 10 to 30 seconds. Do the same with the other leg.

Standing quadriceps stretch: grab a chair with your left hand. Bend your right knee, and, using your right hand, grab your leg by the ankle. Hold this position for 10 to 30 seconds. Do the same with the other leg.

Overhead side stretch: sit in a chair with your feet shoulder-width apart and raise your arms over your head, keep your torso long, and lean to the left. Hold this position for 10 to 30 seconds. Do the same with the other arm.

Shoulder stretch: stand and grab one of your arms with your opposite hand and slowly, pull your arm across your chest until you start to feel a stretch in your shoulder. Hold this position for 10 to 30 seconds. Do the same with the other arm.

Triceps stretch: stand and raise both arms over your head, bending your right arm so that it's positioned behind your head. Place your left hand on your right elbow and gently pull your elbow down towards your back until you begin to feel stretching in your upper arm. Hold this stretch for 10 to 30 seconds

Karate technique

The second part of the class was focused on the performance of Karate basic “kion” techniques, a block and a counterattack. The performed sequences were: gedan barai (lower block) and gyaku zuki (punch), age uke (upper block) and gyaku zuki, uchi uke (middle block) and gyaku zuki, Soto uke (middle block) and gyaku zuki, Mae-Geri (front kick) and gyaku zuki. The sequences were performed in the standing position or in “zengo sudachi” according to participants’ physical abilities. In any case, the Mae-Geri was played holding the wall or the chair with one hand to avoid falls and balance incidents.

Focus

The third part of the class involved games aimed to improve participants' focus. For example: on the count of one lift your right arm, on the count of two the left one, on the count of three lift right and left.

Muscle strengthening exercises

The last part of the class was focused on light strength training for lower limbs and balance, similar to the OTAGO exercise program which is a very well-known and effective program used in many falls' prevention interventions²⁸⁷. Exercises included:

Knee extensor

- sit in a chair with your back well supported.
- straighten the leg out.
- lower the leg.

Knee flexor

- stand up tall facing a table with both hands on the table.
- bend the knee, bringing the foot toward your bottom.
- return to the starting position.

Hip adductor

- stand up tall beside a table and hold onto it.
- keep the exercising leg straight and the foot facing straight ahead.
- lift the leg out to the side and return.
- repeat 10 times.

- turn around.
- repeat this exercise with the other leg

One leg stand

- stand up tall beside the table.
- hold on and look ahead.
- stand on one leg.
- try to hold this position for 10 seconds.
- stand on the other leg.
- try to hold this position for 10 seconds

Sit to stand

- sit on a chair that is not too low.
- place your feet behind your knees.
- lean forward over your knees.
- stand up without using your hands.

All exercises were performed at 10 repetitions²⁸⁸.

At the end of the class, participants were asked to share feedback with the instructor and to complete the scope form questionnaire and a survey about the class.

Measures

The goal of the study was to measure the feasibility and acceptability of the adapted online Karate class.

To assess the feasibility, the research team evaluated recruitment, retention and adherence²⁸⁹. To evaluate the recruitment, the authors considered the total number of people that accepted to take part in the study. For retention, the authors considered all the participants that completed the questionnaire and the class. For adherence, the authors considered all subjects that were able to complete the Karate class.

To assess acceptability, the research team evaluated the extent to which people receiving the intervention considered it to be appropriate, based on cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention²⁹⁰.

To evaluate so, the authors considered the outcomes of the survey “appendix c” and peoples’ oral feedback after the class.

Results

Feasibility and acceptability

Most participants (70%) were recruited thanks to cooperation with a Scottish association for older adults. 10%, were recruited from an informative campaign on social media and 20% were recruited from local Karate schools in Scotland. The research team was able to reach 35 subjects meeting the basic criteria but only 15 were accepted to complete the study. Two were excluded because of age, one was unable or unwilling to use remote technology, three did not attend the session intervention, and four did not complete the questionnaire. The remaining 10 were not interested or did not have the time to participate in the study. Therefore, the study had an adherence and retention of the 43%. Most participants were able to join with no difficulties; only two people had issues to login in the first place and had to ask for remote assistance by calling the Karate instructor on the phone. After that, everybody was able to join the class. Three participants believed that some strength exercises were too easy for them so the instructor invited them to increase the number of repetitions from 10 to 15. On the other hand, during the practice

of Karate techniques, 2 individuals felt a bit overwhelmed by the learning of new techniques so the instructor asked them to stop and rest for 2 minutes, while the others kept practising. 12 participants found the class to be “extremely helpful”, one participant considered it “very helpful” and another other two considered it a “little helpful”. All 15 participants claimed to have learned something new and that the Karate instructor was friendly and approachable. 10 participants answered that the most successful aspect of the program was to be able to meet virtually their old friends. The other five people did not answer. Anyway, all 15 adults would recommend a Karate class as an intervention for their target group. The other five claimed that they would be happy to repeat the same class the next week.

Delivery issue

One of the difficulties was to focus the attention on the athletes performing at the same time on the monitor. To avoid distractions and to improve people’s safety, the team decided to open each online session to a maximum of five participants. At the same time, as the class instructor was one, sometimes he needed to stop to observe participants’ performances and/or take field notes. Even if this was not a major problem, the authors suggest that one might support the Karate instructor focusing on people's performance and safety, while he delivers the training.

Evaluation of data collection procedures:

All participants were able to understand and complete the scope questionnaire even if a few questions were not answered by some of them and the pdf/word format created some issues as the 80% was not familiar with how to fill a pdf or word document. Most subjects answered all questions, but five of them did not. It is not clear if they did not answer for privacy, lack of interest or because they were not careful.

Anyway, as previously stated, it is difficult to compare this research experience and results with previous ones as not many used the scope short form in this population target.

Evaluation of suitability of intervention:

All classes followed the same scheme starting from warming up/stretching to physical exercise to Karate techniques and stretching again. However, the instructor had to adapt each class and exercise to abilities of the volunteers. Communication was very important, and the instructor asked for every exercise how it made them feel. 3 participants believed that some strength exercises were too easy for them, so the instructor invited them to increase the number of repetitions from 10 to 15. On the other hand, during the practice of Karate techniques, 2 individuals felt a bit overwhelmed by the learning of new techniques so the instructor asked them to stop and rest for 2 minutes, while the others kept practising.

All subjects completed the session with no injury or incident. There was no reported burden of participation by the subjects involved. At the end of the class, the instructor asked for some feedback about the training. All participants claimed verbally, at the end of the class, to be satisfied with the service and that they had a good time. Some of them even asked to plan it on a more regular basis

Evaluation of resources and implementation

The adapted Karate instructor used an average domestic internet bandwidth and a chair that was needed to show seniors how to perform some exercises and what to use in the exercise in case of balance issues. Only two people had issues to login in the first place and had to ask for remote assistance by calling the Karate instructor on the phone. Besides this first difficulty, there was no technical interruption or major difficulty related to the technical tools.

Evaluation for further investigation

Ten participants asked spontaneously to continue the session on a more regular basis. Most of them said it was fun, enjoyable and gave them the opportunity to see members of the same age.

Discussions

The study shows that participants were quite satisfied with the intervention as most of them found the class to be “extremely helpful”, or “very helpful” and all participants claimed to have learned something new. The intervention, even if online showed a good outcome for the development of social interactions. In fact, most subjects claimed that the most successful aspect of the program was to be able to meet virtually with other friends. Furthermore, all adults would recommend Karate class as an intervention for their target group and five claimed that they would be happy to repeat the same class the next week. The success of the online class might be due to different reasons such as the easy delivery, the low cost and the possibility to interact with others, but also to the experience of the trainer, described as very friendly and approachable, facilitating the inclusion of all. Results show that the feasibility and acceptability of the intervention were quite good with 43% conversion rate and 100% adherence. In fact, comparing with the existing literature, previous similar studies report a conversion rate of 49% and adherence of 77%²⁸³. In the study by Buckinx et al. To evaluate feasibility and acceptability of remote physical exercise programs to prevent mobility loss in pre-disabled older adults during isolation periods such as the Covid-19 pandemic, the adherence rate was 82.5% in the web-ex group and 85.8% in the booklet group²⁹¹. These differences might depend on the fact that other studies included a larger number of participants and a longer period of intervention.

Most participants were comfortable with the use of remote technology and found the online platform quite easy to use. Furthermore, given the intervention completion rate of 100% and the successful delivery of the intervention, we propose that the online adapted Karate class intervention is feasible to run in a larger fully powered trial to ascertain its effectiveness in changing sedentary behaviour and improving health and well-being in later life. The adherence to the program and the oral feedbacks shows, as in previous studies, that older adults were quite comfortable with the use of remote technology. Hague et al. Assessed the acceptability of a mobile app to support falls rehabilitation, reporting that older adults had few issues with the technology, and were comfortable with using it for exercise advice²⁹². Other studies have suggested that older adults find technological tools as activity trackers acceptable^{293,294}.

On the other hand, it is important to consider the sampling target, given the need for people to own an up-to-date smartphone or computer able to connect to the online platform. Our sample was predominantly educated and retired able to use online technology. On the other hand, if two-thirds of adults in the UK have a smartphone and many of them have also fully embraced digital technology, just 33 per cent of those aged 75 and over have recently used the internet^{294,295}, showing the risk that they will be left behind in our increasingly digital world²⁹⁵. Therefore, more research is needed across a wider demographic to understand whether an online adapted Karate class can truly reach groups such as those from lower-socioeconomic backgrounds and therefore achieve their full potential.

About the delivery of the program, beside the necessity to find an experienced and qualified Karate teacher, it is also important to consider that the instructor would likely need a larger space than the participants, so they can be far enough away from the camera for full body views and he/she should be comfortable in the use of the technology. In our case, for the instructor, it was a little more difficult to find a point of view in front of the camera that allowed participants to observe the Karate exercises and

techniques at the same time, but this problem was overcome by showing exercises from different directions. Nevertheless, most participants were happy to be involved in such online events and asked for other classes on a more regular basis. Considering the Covid-19 restrictions during the intervention and that the research could not benefit from face-to-face meetings or inductions, this was a great result.

It is also worth noting that this web-based exercise intervention demonstrated a high level of safety, as evidenced by the complete absence of adverse incidents during its implementation. This safety profile is further reinforced by findings from a recent systematic review²⁹⁶. This review, encompassing a wide range of similar interventions, consistently reported minimal evidence of adverse incidents. This aligns with our observations and highlights a trend of safety in digital exercise programs. The positive safety record of our program, coupled with supportive evidence from the systematic review, underscores the reliability and security of web-based exercise interventions in promoting health and wellness without compromising user safety. Given that our inclusion criteria required participants to have a year of Karate experience, whether the same intervention with novice Karatekas would have the same low incidence of adverse events is not clear. However, the findings of the systematic review²⁹⁶ would suggest it is worth future investigations.

Our study contributes to the expanding body of research on online exercise interventions. The growing interest in this area aligns with the broader trend of incorporating internet-based activities and devices into various facets of everyday life²⁹⁹. There has been a noticeable increase in technology usage across all societal levels, including among individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Leveraging the internet's widespread availability, web-based exercise programs have proven to be both effective and economical. Our findings indicate that older adults, too, can benefit from an internet-based, at-home exercise platform that is not only accessible and affordable but also scalable.

Limitations

A primary limitation of this work is the relatively short duration of the intervention. While this is common in feasibility studies, longer trials tend to have greater drop out rates. An examination of 72 online exercise programs²⁹⁷ revealed broad range of participant dropout rates, which were notably higher in programs extending beyond six months. The authors reported that an important facet of intervention design was to find methods to sustain participant involvement in these programs. Particularly pertinent to this issue is the concept of self-efficacy, which is defined as an individual's belief in their capacity to influence their own actions and behaviors. Research that has assessed self-efficacy²⁹⁸ through established scales indicates that individuals who persist in exercise programs tend to exhibit higher levels of self-efficacy. Furthermore, the capacity to adjust the difficulty of the exercise regimen is a key factor in keeping participants engaged, however this was a minor consideration in the present study given the relatively short duration.

Besides the important findings previously mentioned, this study shows some limitations. For example, the experiment was conducted only on a small sample, which is an issue because it gives a very little picture of the elderly population and does not help to face issues related to larger recruitment. Participants were already familiar with Karate as they had to have at least 1 year of previous experience in this or similar martial art. Therefore, it is not clear if the class would work with totally new beginners. The intervention was a one-time class; therefore, it is not clear if the adherence would sustain over longer periods. Being online, it was not possible to exercise sparring or techniques with a partner, but at the same time, this could prevent older adults from contact injuries.

The use of remote technology was the only part of the intervention that has confused some of the participants, but it didn't represent a major issue, as at the end all of them were able to join the class with some guidance over the phone. Other studies using web based exercise for older adults has found that

while trouble shooting connection problems occasionally cause issues for older adults, the actual technology was rarely an issue.²⁹⁸ Indeed that work aligns with the present study in that WiFi dropout or connection issues were rarely the cause of adherence issues, and were usually quite easily resolved.

Conclusions

Considering that acceptability depends on the adherence rate and the satisfaction²⁹¹ of the intervention, the authors feel that given the results, the intervention was quite well accepted by participants. The study demonstrated that an adapted online Karate class is feasible to promote active behaviour among older adults and that the practice of this martial arts in later life seems to be not only potentially effective for health but very engaging too. Besides being online, and very few technological issues, the study shows good adherence to the online martial art classes. Therefore, an online adapted Karate class for older adults is possible, feasible, engaging, and pleasant to practice. Online Karate classes should be considered for future interventions to promote active behaviours in elderly people and to improve their general health and well-being.

Chapter VI- General Discussion

The scoping review revealed that mainly 7 themes were represented in the literature about Karate; musculoskeletal health, cardiovascular health, balanced metabolic effects, neurophysiology, psychology and behaviour, and injury. The review shows that Karate brings similar improvements in health as other high-impact sports, showing better BMD and muscle strength in both young and older female participants^{139,140,164}. Karate performance results in adaptation across the entire neuromuscular system similarly to short-term resistance training¹⁷⁹. Karate training seems very effective to improve balance¹²⁹ and cardiovascular health^{159,142} suggesting that Karate could have beneficial effects on health as other forms of sport participation. Other evidence show that karate training contributes to the maintenance of homeostasis in the body^{185,186}; It may enhance neurological function^{163,165}, and improve people general wellbeing in later years¹²⁹.

This was confirmed by the small pilot study involving older martial artists. Results showed older adults practising martial arts had a generally active and independent lifestyle with different hobbies and a satisfying social inclusion, moving their focus from chronological age to their physical and mental abilities. These results find strong support in a previous research by Fuller and Lloyd where the authors underlined how the practice of martial arts improved well-being perception and social inclusion among participants²¹⁷.

To have a better evidence of the benefits of Karate on wellbeing, the authors decided to measure two parameters of wellbeing as coping and self-esteem among different age groups of Karate athletes. The main findings showed that (1) age was associated with mental disengagement, greater active coping, and problem-focused, which was not related to years of Karate training; (2) greater use of planning and use of

avoidant approaches were associated with increasing age and years of training; (3) increasing age and years of training were associated with greater scores on items related to self-criticism.

Results suggest that independently of age, self-esteem seems to be affected by years of training. This is in line with previous literature concerning self-esteem. Nemcek et al. Showed individuals with higher levels of athletic competence experienced greater self-esteem²⁵⁸.

Considering that Karate is potentially as powerful as other physical activities to improve people general wellbeing in any age and that it seems to be quite popular, but that its use is not very common in the field of Adapted Physical Activity, the authors tried to run a pilot study to evaluate the feasibility and acceptability of an online adapted Karate class for older adults. The study shows that participants were quite happy with the programme and they asked for more classes.

Therefore, Karate should be definitely considered as other effective physical activities to improve older adults' wellbeing.

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Appendix I

A) Ethical Approval Document

05/02/2021

Dear DaniloContiero,

Your application 13878: feasibility and acceptability of a karate intervention in later life, submission reference 13247, has been approved, with conditions, by the Health and Life Sciences SEC. You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below;

Title

Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)

Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)

Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)

Comment

Correct the grammatical errors in the PIS before sending it to potential participants. Remove the formatting markup from the PIS before distributing it.

The PIS still does not state that the interviews will be recorded, it must do so. The section on "what will i be required to do" must tell the participants that their image and voice will be recorded during the interviews.

The multiple statements in the consent form must be separated out into individual statements and the participant asked to agree each one individually (initialling a box for example).

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them. Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix II

B) Chapter III-Interview questions

- 1) Why did you start to practice Martial Arts?
- 2) When did you start to practice Martial Arts?
- 3) .How often do you train?
- 4) How would you describe your usual day?
- 5) Does Martial Arts help your social activity?
- 6) Has Martial Arts helped you to have a better quality of life?
- 7) How was your approach with Martial Arts?
- 8) Are you religious?
- 9) What do you think about Martial Arts?
- 10) Is your family support important?
- 11) Training with younger people helps?

C) Chapter V- Acceptability

- 1) How helpful did you find the Karate class intervention overall? A) not at all helpful b) a little helpful c) moderately helpful d) very helpful e) extremely helpful- please explain:
- 2) To what extent do you agree or disagree with these statements about the Karate class intervention:
- 3) I learnt new things about Karate and my physical abilities: a) strongly disagree b) disagree c) neither agree or disagree d) agree e) strongly agree
- 4) The Karate instructor was approachable and friendly: a) strongly disagree b) disagree c)neither agree or disagree d) agree e) strongly agree
- 5) How successful has the program been in helping your relative/friend in his/her caring role (if applicable): a) not at all b) a little c) moderately d) very e) extremely f) don't know g)not relevant
- 6) Please, explain in your own view what were the most successful aspects of the program
- 7) Please, explain in your own view what were the least successful aspects of the program

- 8) Can you think of ways in which the program can be improved?
- 9) Would you recommend the Karate class intervention to others? Why?
- 10) Would you like to repeat the Karate class intervention? Why? If yes, how often?
- 11) When the intervention ended, did you continue to benefit from the “treatment”?
- 12) Do you have any other comments about the Karate intervention or about the study?